

ERA-NET Cofund on Blue Bioeconomy (BlueBio) – Unlocking the Potential of Aquatic Bioresources

SMARTCHAIN

Smart solutions for advancing supply systems in blue bioeconomy value chains

Start date of project: 01/10/2021

Duration: 36 Months

Deliverable: D3.3

Key leverage points and role of actors

Synthesis of key leverage points and role of actors to progress towards circularity and enhanced sustainability in the blue bioeconomy supply chain.

SmartChain

Blue Bioeconomy Solutions

Project co-funded country funding agencies in Norway, Denmark, Iceland, and Romania and the European Commission within the H2020 Programme as ERA-NET Cofund on Blue Bioeconomy (BlueBio) – Unlocking the Potential of Aquatic Bioresources project No.817992

Dissemination level of this deliverable

PU	Public	X
CO	Confidential, only for members of the consortium (including the Funding Agencies)	
RE	Restricted to a group specified by the consortium (including the Funding Agencies)	
CI	Classified, information as referred to in Commission Decision 2001/844/EC.	

“This project has received ERA-NET co-funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817992”

/nnovation Fund Denmark

Document Status Sheet

Due date of deliverable:	Month no. 36
Actual submission date:	November 2024
Partner in charge of the deliverable and contributing partners	University of Iceland SINTEF Ocean
Contact person responsible for this deliverable:	Gudrun Olafsdottir Email: go@hi.is
Authors:	Nína M. Saviolidis, Gudrun Olafsdottir
Version	3.0
Document Status	Final

Change history:

Version	Date	Details (additions, changes, reviews, performed by whom)
1.0	21.10.2024	Draft report v.3 uploaded on shared folder for partners comments
2.0	26.11.2024	Final v.6 uploaded on shared project folder
3.0	29.01.2026	Final v.7 /Table 4 updated and reference added – uploaded to zenodo

Disclaimer:

This report reflects only the authors' view, and the respective National Funding Agencies and EU Funding Agency are not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Citation:

Saviolidis, N.M., Olafsdottir, G. (2024). Key leverage points and role of actors. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). Deliverable: D3.2, University of Iceland, Reykjavík, 45 pages. **10.5281/zenodo.18420147**

"This project has received ERA-NET co-funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 817992"

/nnovation Fund Denmark

Technology
Development Fund

CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	4
1. INTRODUCTION	6
Circularity in the context of the bioeconomy	6
Circular business models	6
Sustainability and circularity assessments	7
Life cycle based approaches	8
IMTA and circular economy principles	8
Framework and topics of indicators for circularity and sustainability	10
European sustainability reporting standards (ESRS)	11
2. METHODS	14
2.1 Analysis of companies’ CSR reports	14
2.2 Identification of policy relevant to the circular blue bioeconomy	14
2.3 Synthesis of challenges, leverage points, policy tools and role of actors	14
3. RESULTS	15
3.1 Content Analysis of CSR reports	15
Frameworks standards and initiatives	15
3.2 Governance and policy related to CE	23
3.3 Challenges, leverage points, policy tools and role of actors	26
Sustainability challenges and circularity approaches	26
Barriers to transitioning towards sustainability and circularity	28
Synthesis of challenges, leverage points, policy tools and role of actors	29
4. CONCLUSION	36
5. REFERENCES	37
ANNEX I	45

List of Figures

Figure 1 The Circular Bioeconomy (CBE) Stegman et al. (2020)	6
Figure 2 Topics of indicators selected in SMARTCHAIN D3.1 (Saviolidis et al., 2022) for the sustainability dimensions of the blue bioeconomy system (fisheries and aquaculture)	10
Figure 4 Double materiality as defined in ESRG 1 guidelines	12
Figure 5 Conceptual framework for the circular blue bioeconomy	26
Figure 7 Classification of policy tools with examples. Source: Adapted from Saviolidis et al. (2020), based on Galli et al. (2020)	29

List of Tables

Table 1 Sector specific “Likely material topics” GRI 13 Agriculture, Aquaculture and Fishing Sectors 2022	11
Table 2 CSR Reporting in aquaculture companies in Norway and Iceland	16
Table 3 Examples of initiatives, certifications and frameworks applied by companies in fisheries and aquaculture sectors in Iceland and Norway	17
Table 4 ESRS material topics and topics reported by companies in aquaculture sectors in Iceland and Norway	18
Table 5 Key policies and strategies relevant to the bioeconomy	24
Table 6 Summary and selected findings from stakeholder interviews on the perception of challenges and barriers in Iceland and Norway (Source: SMARTCHAIN Deliverable 3.2. Saviolidis et al. 2023)	28
Table 7 Challenges, leverage points, policy tools and key actors responsible for motivating enhanced sustainability and circular bioeconomy in fisheries and aquaculture value chains in Iceland and Norway (further information “notes” listed below)	30
Table 8 List of the largest fisheries companies in Iceland according to catch volumes (Aflamark) in 2022-2023 and information on sustainability reporting and certifications from their websites (From Deliverable 3.2)	45

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The general aim of the SMARTCHAIN project, is to develop approaches and tools for sustainable utilisation, production planning, logistics optimisation, and traceability to facilitate transfer of bio-resources from catch/production throughout the value chain of fisheries and aquaculture products. This report is part of WP3 “*Sustainable resource use and circularity*” which has three main objectives; (1) to identify relevant frameworks and indicators for monitoring the sustainability dimensions of the blue bioeconomy; (2) to explore stakeholders’ views on barriers and drivers that affect the circularity transformation of the blue bioeconomy through in-depth interviews; (3) finally, to examine the impacts of governance and policy dynamics in blue bioeconomy value chains (fisheries and aquaculture sectors) by assessing key leverage points and role of actors in motivating circularity and innovation towards sustainability.

ADVANCING THE CBE IN ICELAND AND NORWAY – CASE STUDY

The SMARTCHAIN case study “*Circularity in the blue bioeconomy value chain*” focuses on sustainability criteria and circular bioeconomy objectives. The blue bioeconomy entails the production of renewable aquatic biological resources and the conversion of these resources and waste streams into value added products, such as food, feed, bio-based products and bioenergy. Iceland and Norway represent interesting case studies because they both have economically significant blue bioeconomy sectors especially in the fisheries and aquaculture sectors and important secondary and supporting industries. Overall, the SMARTCHAIN project explores the sustainability challenges and enablers to circular bioeconomy as well as identifying policy gaps and recommendations on policy integration and strategies to facilitate the transition to circular blue bioeconomy.

The SMARTCHAIN project explores challenges and enablers for the transformation to circular blue bioeconomy using fisheries and aquaculture sectors in Iceland and Norway as case studies, and examines the status of organisational motivation for enhanced sustainability performance and circularity

OBJECTIVES

The objective of *T3.3 Governance of blue bioeconomy supply chains and scenario approaches for innovative business models* is to explore multistakeholder processes and governance aspects of aquaculture and fisheries supply chains by assessing policy implementation regarding circularity strategies and regulations.

This activity is supported by the SMARTCHAIN_policy top-up project and links to work on sustainability indicators conducted earlier in the SMARTCHAIN project¹, followed by research on stakeholder perception of the key barriers to transforming fisheries and aquaculture food supply systems towards more sustainable and circular bioeconomic systems². The work here involves systematically examining, policies and standards which companies use in the CSR reporting, including initiatives, assessment approaches and metrics (indicators) used by companies to measure their performance in terms of circularity (where available) and sustainability (as related to circularity); which targets have companies set and whether

¹ Saviolidis, N.M., Olafsdottir, G. (2022). *Deliverable: D3.1*, University of Iceland, Reykjavík

² Saviolidis, N.M., Olafsdottir, G, Mehta S., Strand, A.V. Myhre, M.S., and Bogason, S. (2023). *Deliverable: D3.2*, University of Iceland, Reykjavík

company level actions can contribute meaningfully to the advancement of circular blue bioeconomy strategies in Iceland and Norway.

KEY OUTCOME

The first part of the report, is based on literature and covers definitions and examples of circular business models in the context of the blue bioeconomy, followed by discussion and examples of sustainability and circularity assessments and highlighting the benefits of life cycle-based approaches. Frameworks that companies use and topics of indicators for circularity and sustainability assessment were explored along with the requirements of the European Sustainability Reporting Standards (ESRS).

The explorative review of sustainability reports of fisheries and aquaculture companies gave insight into the organisational approaches to sustainability and circularity, and furthermore the key policies and strategies relevant to the bioeconomy that have been formulated at international, regional and national levels were reviewed.

The research outcome is a synthesis of the challenges, key leverage points, policy and role of industry actors including the role of respective stakeholders, NGOs and governments in the blue bioeconomy supply chain. The focus was on identifying leverage points where improvements can be made to enhance circularity and innovation towards sustainability specifically for the fisheries and aquaculture sectors.

NEXT STEPS

Further synthesis of the results is in progress and manuscripts are forthcoming for scientific publications which will support and substantiate policy implications.

1. INTRODUCTION

CIRCULARITY IN THE CONTEXT OF THE BIOECONOMY

A sustainable bioeconomy is the renewable segment of the circular economy (COM, 2018). It relies on biological resources to produce goods and services and involves all sectors and systems which rely on biological resources such as agriculture, forestry, fisheries, aquaculture and biotechnology, among others. The blue bioeconomy is the sustainable use of aquatic resources and ecosystems. The focus is on turning bio-waste, residues, and discards into valuable resources, and/or recycling nutrients (Figure 1). The overarching circular bioeconomy (CBE) principles are resource efficiency, optimizing value of biomass over time and sustainability (Stegman (2020)).

The circular economy (CE) has the potential to contribute to other dimensions of sustainability beyond the environmental ones (Geissdoerfer et al., 2017) and even supporting several SDG goals while contributing to innovative business and management models. Moreover, the circular economy is recognised as a powerful framework to achieve transformative change as it creates value in ways that rebuild biodiversity and provide other society-wide benefit (EMF, 2021)

Figure 1 The Circular Bioeconomy (CBE) Stegman et al. (2020)

CIRCULAR BUSINESS MODELS

A transition towards a circular economy for the blue bioeconomy can contribute to resource efficiency gains which are integral to sustainable development. At the same time, it can also stimulate increased profit by turning waste streams or lower value products into value or higher value streams. The transition thus entails new approaches for the industries. The new circular business models can provide opportunities for enhanced sustainability, however, the key driver for new business models is typically economic benefits.

Despite political interest and motivation of CE from international institutions and organisations, there is a lack of common understanding of the concept of circular economy, the criteria, indicators and metrics to assess circular economy performance of both regions and organizations (Ho et al., 2023; Valls-Val et al., 2022; Kirchherr et al., 2017; 2023, Geissdoerfer, et al., 2020).

Circular business models entail value creation and sustainable use of resources, reducing food loss and waste (FLW) and closing resource loops

In the blue bioeconomy (fisheries and aquaculture) the focus is on enhancing the utilisation of rest raw materials (RRM) into value added products, minimizing discards and FLW and closing biowaste resource streams to produce e.g. fertilisers and biogas.

Richardson (2008) defined the major components of a business model as (i) value proposition, (ii) value creation, and (iii) value capture, while Linder and Williander (2017) defined a circular business model as a business strategy in which the conceptual logic for value creation is based on utilizing the residual economic value of products post-use in the production of new offerings. Similarly, Bocken et al., (2016) discuss business model strategies that support both slowing and closing resource loops - involve capturing value from what would otherwise be considered “waste” in a linear business. However, Bocken and Short, (2021) stated that sectoral progress on business model innovation has been insufficient to address much of the social and environmental harm caused by, or facilitated by industry, and progress against the SDGs goals has been disappointing.

Another approach to slow resource loops is a product-service system (PSS) business model strategy (Sousa Zomer et al., 2018). For example, renting of tubs in the seafood industry represents a circular business which offers functionality (in a renting scheme) instead of products.

SUSTAINABILITY AND CIRCULARITY ASSESSMENTS

The development of approaches for the assessment of CE practices is gradually emerging partly motivated by regulatory requirements but also motivated by voluntary initiatives of companies seeing benefit of using circularity approaches to enhance the sustainability and profitability of their activities and products. The reporting of circularity generally includes Inputs, Production and Outputs, where greenhouse gas emission (GHG) is the most common circularity aspect reported followed by Total Energy Consumed and Waste generation (Ibanez- Forés, 2022). A lack of CE reporting was observed in environmental reporting of manufacturing companies in EU who mainly report on reduction of resource use but in general a lack of reporting the “reuse, recycling, and recovery” circularity principles. In the case of the manufacturing companies, it was noted that disclosures and the KPIs should be designed better to reflect activities of closing the loop (e.g. recycle, recover), as well as slowing the loops (e.g. reduce, reuse (remanufacture)). This implies that the CE reporting is still weak and lacks standards and guidance for companies who mainly seek to legitimate their own position and actions by reflecting institutional logics that are centered on best practices (Dagiliene et al., 2020).

The use of circularity and sustainability assessment approaches varies among companies depending on sector, type of activity and size according to a study conducted in 2020 among Italian and Dutch companies in manufacturing, construction and other service activities (Lindgreen et al., 2021). The reporting framework used by the companies is generally environmental accounting (EA) or GRI and most often they use sustainability indicators based on direct impact and apply life cycle assessments to CE strategies. However, the use of different type of indicators and metrics has caused confusion and comparison is difficult. Based on the study by Lindgreen et al. (2021), life cycle-based footprint approaches like CF (carbon footprint) were most often used in manufacturing companies, followed by EF (ecological footprint), PEF (product environmental footprint), MFA (material flow analysis), LCC (life cycle costing), WF (water footprint) and social-LCA was least common. Use of single indicators like volume of waste diverted to landfill, recycling rate or recycled content are common, followed by virgin material production prevented, material durability, volume of non-renewable resources not extracted, time for disassembly and least common is the material circularity indicator. Overall, tailormade sustainability or circularity indicators based on LCA approach or direct impact are commonly applied by the companies.

LIFE CYCLE BASED APPROACHES

Life cycle thinking and life cycle assessment (LCA) is widely used to assess the environmental and sustainability performance of a system, technology, process, or product (Ruiz-Salmón et al., 2021). The benefit of LCA approach is the standardized methodology for greenhouse gas emission accounting (CF) and the ability to explore different environmental impacts across products' production, usage and disposal stages. However, a contradiction can arise between LCA studies, depending on methodology, where by-product use is both encouraged and discouraged at the same time depending on the boundaries of the study and allocation (Ayer et al 2007; Svanes et al., 2011, Ruiz-Salmón et al. 2021).

Despite limitations of the LCA methodological approach regarding allocation and boundaries of different studies, the LCA is well suited to compare and assess environmental performance in terms of life cycle based environmental impacts of circularity approaches, and innovations as reported by Cristiano et al. (2022). LCIA indicators to assess e.g. global warming potential, eutrophication, acidification, human toxicity impacts, land occupation and biochemical oxygen demand among others, were used to assess the treatment and valorisation of sludge with end-of-life recovery of nutrients and biomass to be reused as organic fertiliser or as energy source, and a new device for drying fish mortalities and reusing the end-product as ingredient in the pet food industry or as energy source. The result of the assessment from finfish aquaculture showed reduction of impacts for almost all LCIA indicators, but the end-of-life scenarios for recirculated organic material are subject to social acceptability issues, e.g. when reusing aquaculture discards as pet food, or when using bio-gas as an energy source while tackling climate change (Cristiano et al., 2022).

Gaps in measuring sustainability performance have been identified e.g. in the 'seafood' water-energy-food nexus literature, the water usage in seafood production has been overlooked (Gephart et al. (2017). Furthermore, a recent review of organizational approaches to CE in CSR reporting of companies reveals that there is still an absence of standardised reporting principles and procedures for publishing progress on circularity and a clear disconnection between CE and sustainability reporting literature (Opferkuch et al., 2021). A "nexus thinking" approach (i.e. the analysis of actions in connected systems) combined with life cycle thinking appears as an excellent opportunity to motivate the transition to a circular economy (Ruiz-Salomon et al., 2020). The water-energy-food nexus of different treatment options of rest raw material: anaerobic digestion, in-vessel composting, incineration, and landfilling were explored by LCA. The results showed that anaerobic digestion was the most sustainable and in-vessel composting the least (Storach et al., 2020). Similarly, Laso et al. (2016) analysed the environmental impact of anchovy waste valorisation in contrast to incineration and landfilling and the valorisation waste management options resulted in the least impact on the environment.

IMTA AND CIRCULAR ECONOMY PRINCIPLES

Integrated multi trophic aquaculture (IMTA) system is a form of circulatory approach for a more sustainable aquaculture where simultaneous production of aquaculture species e.g. fish, molluscs and seaweed are aimed at improving the efficiency and the ecosystem health. A recent review by Hala et al., (2024) analysed 29 LCA studies on IMTA systems from 2009 to 2022 to understand the challenges, limitations, and benefits of LCA methodologies on IMTA systems. As for aquaculture in general, the provision and use of feed, fish effluents, and energy use are the impact hotspots and improving these factors might decrease the total impacts of the system as well. The study concludes on the need for the development of a specific database for the aquaculture sector, together with a standardized methodology for Data Collection and definition of impact categories to improve the consistency and comparability of the studies. Similarly, Ziegler et al. (2024) emphasised that in addition to the systematic collection of robust data for more continuous monitoring of GHG emission

performance over time, there is a need to identify and monitor additional indicators to ensure the seafood sector develops not only towards climate neutrality but also towards broader sustainability.

The opportunities and limitations for the introduction of circular economy principles in EU aquaculture were explored with a focus on the regulatory framework (Regueiro et al., 2022). A new concept for aquaculture models was suggested by integrating CE and including technologies from recirculation to the implementation of IMTA and biofloc schemes, or using sludge for biogas production, co-incineration or fertilizers. However, the authors state that more effort is required to overcome socioeconomic, logistic, and legislative barriers, as well as producers' and consumers' habits, to address current problems, such as climate change or waste production, linking ecological and socioeconomic development (Regueiro et al., 2022).

For seafood by-product valorisation, the consideration of the use and implementation of the enabling technologies and approaches are needed and the sustainability of interventions and actions needs to balance the economic and environmental needs of society and business operators (Cooney et al., 2024). The implementation of circular business models has in general been slow partly because of the dependence of businesses on linear models. Apart from some R&D investments, development of the bioeconomy is mainly left to the market which can sometimes undermine broader sustainability goals so it's important to critically assess policies and strategies and whether they are synergistic or not (Saviolidis et al., 2023). The realisation of successful circular business models which both slow down and close resource loops involves a strategic coordination and collaboration of the business partners. Establishment of well working networks throughout the value chains can be a part of the solution to fulfil the transition to the blue circular economy. Advancing the circular blue bioeconomy can also contribute to internationally agreed upon goals: the Sustainable Development Goals.

FRAMEWORK AND TOPICS OF INDICATORS FOR CIRCULARITY AND SUSTAINABILITY

The identification of common indicators to facilitate transparent communication of sustainability status and circularity improvement potentials is crucial. Our earlier work in the SMARTCHAIN project in 2022 was focused on identifying framework and indicators for circularity and sustainability assessment of fisheries and aquaculture industries. Sustainability topics were selected from pre-existing frameworks relevant to the circular blue bioeconomy and including the four sustainability dimensions (Figure 2).

<p>Governance dimension</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Fishery Management Permits /licenses Impact assessment Nature based solutions Strategy and vision Climate change Innovation Certification and labelling Supply chain Sourcing policies Food safety /Nutrition Education of sustainability Risk assessment and management Transparency and accountability 	<p>Environmental dimension</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Status of stock Fishery management Farm management Chemical use Mitigation GHG emissions (Scope1-3) Emissions to air Impact on ecosystems Economic viability (e.g. production, stocking density) Feed management Fish health and welfare Sourcing policies Level of energy consumption Energy efficiency Waste management Wastewater management Water quality Water use efficiency 	<p>Economic dimension</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Concentration of businesses Economic benefits Economic viability (production, size) Processing conditions Employment Financial viability Funding and Costs
		<p>Social dimension</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Employment conditions Health and safety management Inclusiveness and vulnerability (labor) Fairness in remuneration Stakeholder acceptance Social balance

Figure 2 Topics of indicators selected in SMARTCHAIN D3.1 (Saviolidis et al., 2022) for the sustainability dimensions of the blue bioeconomy system (fisheries and aquaculture)

The advantage of using previously developed frameworks and indicator sets to monitor progress, is that extensive review work that was put into their development ensures that the indicators chosen are for the most part already being used in some capacity and that the methodology behind them is well-defined. The COM framework was at the time (in 2022) insufficient to cover fisheries and aquaculture sectors, and therefore, the FAO’s indicators for the bioeconomy were added and cross referenced with GRI including criteria of fisheries and farm management, and specific criteria for energy efficiency, waste management and wastewater etc. The final selection resulted in a dashboard of indicators for the environmental, social, economic and governance dimensions and including sector-specific topics for aquaculture and fisheries (Deliverable 3.1). The topics for CE assessment are closely linked to sustainability in general but the issues on efficient resource use, waste- and wastewater management, energy use/efficiency and emissions are critical.

In 2019, the Global Sustainability Standards Board (GSSB) initiated a project under the Sector Program to develop a Standard for Agriculture, Aquaculture, and Fishing. The GRI 13 Sector standard for Agriculture, Aquaculture and Fishing was published in June 2022 and came into effect for reporting in January 2024 (Table 1).

Table 1 Sector specific “Likely material topics” GRI 13 Agriculture, Aquaculture and Fishing Sectors 2022

<p>Environmental and social topics</p> <p>13.1 Emissions</p> <p>13.2 Climate adaptation and resilience</p> <p>13.3 Biodiversity</p> <p>13.4 Natural ecosystem conversion</p> <p>13.5 Soil health</p> <p>13.6 Pesticides use</p> <p>13.7 Water and effluents</p> <p>13.8 Waste</p> <p>13.9 Food security</p> <p>13.10 Food safety</p> <p>13.11 Animal health and welfare</p> <p>Social and Governance topics</p> <p>13.12 Local communities</p> <p>13.13 Land and resource right</p>	<p>13.14 Rights of indigenous peoples</p> <p>13.15 Non-discrimination and equal opportunity</p> <p>13.16 Forced or compulsory labour</p> <p>13.17 Child labour</p> <p>13.18 Freedom of association and collective bargaining</p> <p>13.19 Occupational health and safety</p> <p>13.20 Employment practices</p> <p>13.21 Living income and living wage</p> <p>13.22 Economic inclusion</p> <p>13.23 Supply chain traceability</p> <p>13.24 Public policy</p> <p>13.25 Anti-competitive behavior</p> <p>13.26 Anti-corruption</p>
---	---

EUROPEAN SUSTAINABILITY REPORTING STANDARDS (ESRS)

The new European sustainability reporting standards (ESRS) which were adopted in July 2023³ and supplementing the Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) (Directive (EU) 2022/2464, 2022) are tailored to EU policies, particularly the Green Deal, while building on and contributing to international standardization initiatives. The aim is to harmonise and motivate a common approach for companies and streamline the documentation required by standards and reporting.

The ESRS cover Cross cutting standards on General requirements and General disclosures. Sustainability matters are covered in ESRS Topical standards in three areas: 1) Environment: Climate change, pollution, water and marine resources, biodiversity, and circular economy; 2) Social: Own workforce, workers in the value chain, affected communities, and consumers and end-users; 3) Governance: Business conduct.

The ESRS standards are aligned to the EU’s environmental objectives: Climate change mitigation, climate change adaptation, sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources, transition to circular economy (foster the efficient use of resources promote recycling, and minimize waste generation), pollution prevention and control (air water and soil), protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems. Furthermore, the ESRS environmental topic “Circular Economy” includes the subtopics: resources inflows (resource use); resources outflows related to products and services; and waste. Consistent with the EU’s environmental objectives, there has been increased awareness in the aquaculture and fisheries sectors in Iceland and Norway on sustainable use of resources and

ESRS 5: Resource use and circular economy

- Resources inflows including resource use
- Resource outflows related to products and services
- Waste

“The goal is to maximise and maintain the value of the resources, products and materials by creating a system that allows for renewability, long life optimal use or re-use, refurbishment, remanufacturing, recycling and biodegradation” (EFRAG, 2022)

³ Commission Delegated Regulation (EU) 2023/2772 of 31 July 2023 supplementing Directive 2013/34/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council as regards sustainability reporting standards <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX:32023R2772>

circularity, and a focus on enhancing the utilisation of rest raw materials (RRM) into value added products, minimizing food loss and waste (FLW) and closing biowaste resource streams to produce fertilisers and biogas.

In addition to the CSRD, the EU has also issued the EU Taxonomy⁴ which classifies economic activities and defines which activities are environmentally sustainable. The EU Taxonomy has set 6 environmental objectives that represent an EU strategic vision and are aligned with the topical ESRS environmental standards (Climate change mitigation, Climate change adaptation, Sustainable use and protection of water and marine resources, Transition to circular economy, Pollution prevention and control, Protection and restoration of biodiversity and ecosystems).

The largest companies (listed and non-listed) are currently preparing and adapting their reporting practices to fulfil the requirements according to the new ESRS standard with the first reports using the standard to be published in 2025 (with 2024 data). In general, there is a trend towards more mandatory reporting around the world with the European Union leading the way (KPMG, 2022)⁵.

Voluntary reporting remains significant with various standards being used such as the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI), the Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP), the Sustainability Accounting Standards Board (SASB) standards among others.

The ESRS standards were developed in alignment with the GRI (i.e. ensuring interoperability) (EFRAG, 2024)⁶ which is one of the most used voluntary reporting standards around the world (KPMG, 2022).

The ESRS standards are aimed at facilitating a more comparable approach to the sustainability and circularity assessment.

However, *improvements in approaches to CE assessment are needed* to facilitate a transparent communication of the performance and notably, enhanced collaboration with the upstream and downstream actors and stakeholders involved in the supply chain is crucial to capture the whole life cycle of products and the circular activities.

Figure 3 Double materiality as defined in ESG 1 guidelines

⁴ <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2020/852/oj> (EU Taxonomy: Regulation (EU) 2020/852 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 18 June 2020 on the establishment of a framework to facilitate sustainable investment, and amending Regulation (EU) 2019/2088

⁵ <https://kpmg.com/xx/en/our-insights/esg/survey-of-sustainability-reporting-2022/global-trends.html>

⁶ ESRS-ISSB Standards Interoperability Guidance: https://finance.ec.europa.eu/news/corporate-sustainability-reporting-commission-welcomes-guidance-interoperability-european-and-global-2024-05-02_en

The most significant difference in the ESRS standards is in the materiality assessment. Until now materiality assessments have been focused on the impacts of companies and organizations on sustainability aspects (“inside-out” approach). With the ESRS standards companies must conduct a double materiality assessment which has the added perspective of impacts from sustainability aspects on the company (e.g. possible financial risks from climate impacts) (“outside-in” approach).

“Double materiality is the union (in mathematical terms, i.e. union of two sets, not intersection) of impact materiality and financial materiality. A sustainability topic or information meets therefore the criteria of double materiality if it is material from the impact perspective or from the financial perspective or from both of these two perspectives”⁷.

In addition to mandatory reporting, there is also a mandatory limited assurance obligation for companies under the CSRD. EFRAG was tasked with developing sector-agnostic standards to be then supplemented by the development of sector-specific standards. The first sector-specific ESRS standards are currently in the validation and approval phases for the following sectors: Oil and Gas; Mining, quarrying and coal mining; Road transport; Textiles, accessories, footwear and jewellery and financial institutions and likely to be published in 2025. Other sector-specific standards are still in the early draft phase including Agriculture, farming and fishing (EFRAG, 2024)⁸.

The deadline for reporting on sector-specific standards was also postponed through political agreement from mid 2024 to mid 2026 to reduce the administrative burden of companies (COM, 2024)⁹.

The newly published GRI 13 Sector standard for Agriculture, Aquaculture and Fishing provides guidance and criteria for these sectors to improve reporting of circularity and risks associated with biodiversity challenges.

⁷ ESRS 1 Double materiality conceptual guidelines for standard-setting Working paper, January 2022 (Draft)

⁸ <https://www.efrag.org/en/sustainability-reporting/esrs-workstreams/sectorspecific-esrs>

⁹ https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/mex_24_707

2. METHODS

2.1 ANALYSIS OF COMPANIES' CSR REPORTS

The objective is to explore/review the use of frameworks and indicators for sustainability and circular bioeconomy assessment in CSR reports of companies. The material topics and indicators applied in the actual reporting in CSR reports are aligned with the new ESRS standards

Company reports for review were selected from fisheries and aquaculture in Iceland and Norway using a list of the largest companies in fisheries according to allowable catch (Aflamark in 2023) and for aquaculture we selected the companies with the largest number of aquaculture sites ASC certified¹⁰ in Norway (353 sites) and three companies (8 sites) listed from Iceland all with Norwegian ownership.

Content analysis of companies CSR reports gives insights to the organisational approaches to sustainability and circularity.

The study is limited by availability of CSR reports on the websites of the companies

2.2 IDENTIFICATION OF POLICY RELEVANT TO THE CIRCULAR BLUE BIOECONOMY

In the SMARTCHAIN project the governance and policy dynamics of the blue bioeconomy value chains and sectors are evidenced from the ground level of policy implementation regarding circularity strategies and regulation and drawing from results of interviews conducted with seafood industry, policy officials and other stakeholders in Iceland and Norway (D3.2, Saviolidis et al., 2024). The governance aspects include for example the market and supply chain structures, social aspects, power, and information asymmetries amongst value chain actors, and how collaboration and sharing of information is best achieved.

The objective is to explore/review current policies relevant to the CBE and the role of governance in facilitating the transition to a more sustainable and circular blue bioeconomy

2.3 SYNTHESIS OF CHALLENGES, LEVERAGE POINTS, POLICY TOOLS AND ROLE OF ACTORS

The overall synthesis considers the overall SMARTCHAIN results e.g. outcome of the mapping of sustainability hotspots in WP1 and the identified barriers to enhanced sustainability and circularity, based on in depth interviews in WP3. Traceability in WP4 and potential technical and modelling innovations in WP2 and WP5 are also considered in the synthesis and then further supported by recent literature.

The synthesis is aimed at identifying leverage points, policy gaps and the role of actors to motivate sustainability and circular blue bioeconomy

¹⁰ <https://asc-aqua.org/find-a-farm/> checked in Oct 2024 a list of 631 sites including operations in Norway, Chile, Scotland/UK, Canada, Australia, Faroe Islands and Iceland

3. RESULTS

3.1 CONTENT ANALYSIS OF CSR REPORTS

Sustainability reports may play an important role as a supporting tool in the transition of organisations towards more circular economy models, since their content can help to measure, monitor, and communicate the organisations' transition and to establish goals in the short/medium term (Ibáñez- Forés et al., 2022). The content analysis of CSR reports is aligned with the work in the Bluebio Cofunded top-up project Smartchain_policy. The aim is to extend the Smartchain project's work on sustainability indicators by analysing company reports from Iceland and Norway to investigate what targets the private sector has set and how it measures its performance in achieving those targets (which specific metrics do companies use). This research activity extends the Smartchain project's tasks on sustainability indicators, data availability and transparency through the systematic analysis of reporting and standards.

There are several limitations and concerns about CSR reporting addressed in the literature to be taken into consideration in analysing reports. Some of the main issues are lack of standardization, greenwashing and selective disclosure, reliability issues, and whether reporting covers the core business and most impactful areas of the company's operations. Perhaps the most debated issue is whether these reports are mostly impression management (Talbot & Boiral, 2018) rather than genuine engagement with sustainability issues. Studies have investigated obfuscation tactics in reports using graphs (Cho et al., 2012), photos (Kanbaty et al., 2024), infographics (Kanbaty et al., 2020) as well as various techniques to rationalize negative impacts especially in understudied topics (Boiral, 2016) and in high-impact sectors (Talbot & Boiral, 2018; Zharfpeykan, 2021). The role of assurance companies as third-party independent assessors of the content and quality of reports has also been researched, critically evaluated and found to be lacking necessary credibility (Hazaea et al., 2022; Boiral & Heras-Saizarbitoria, 2020).

Considering these critical perspectives and the scepticism surrounding voluntary reporting by companies it is perhaps not so surprising that reporting trends show that the practice is becoming increasingly more mandatory falling under the purview of governmental bodies (KPMG, 2022). The EU CSRD addresses some of these criticisms by mandating reporting on certain core sustainability issues, specifying the metrics, and increasing the responsibility of assurance providers (from limited to reasonable assurance). Some EU states may go further still e.g. by following the example of France which imposes penalties (fines and sentences) for non-compliance with sustainability disclosures (Foley, 2023).

FRAMEWORKS STANDARDS AND INITIATIVES

Guidelines on CSR reporting (e.g. ESG, GRI) have motivated reporting on defined indicators and the trend is that companies in the fisheries sectors in Iceland are making efforts to report on their activities for enhanced transparency to meet current requirements. According to our preliminary study in 2023 (SMARTCHAIN D3.2), companies in the fisheries sector in Iceland generally support UN Global Compact SDG's and the reports are prepared in accordance with the GRI Standard (Global Reporting Initiative GRI100-400) and Fisheries Iceland's and Nasdaq's ESG reporting guide 2.0¹¹. The non-financial information and indicators used in CSR reports by the largest Icelandic fisheries companies are focused on issues reflecting improvements that are needed to tackle the key sustainability challenges mainly climate change impact. The environmental indicators used in the companies' reports are on

¹¹ <https://www.nasdaq.com/docs/2019/11/26/2019-ESG-Reporting-Guide.pdf>

energy/fuel use of the fleet, GHG emissions (a few are reporting Scope 1,2, and 3) and type of waste and recycling (mainly fishing gear).

Among the 15 largest seafood companies analysed in 2023, eight had published their sustainability reports on their websites (SMARTCHAIN D3.2). The social aspects cover for example statements on employee rights and gender equality / equal pay. The companies have certifications listed on their websites such as MSC which has been acquired by all the companies who are also members of ISF (Iceland Sustainable Fisheries). IRF (Iceland Responsible Fisheries) verification of origin, is also common, and fisheries involved in pelagic fisheries are certified against IFFO and FEMAS (feed material assurance). Companies involved in processing have implemented standards approved by GFSI (Global Food Safety Initiative) which is also a new requirement (effective in May 2024) along with ASC certification for large companies who are processing aquaculture products. The companies have signed a joint policy of social responsibility based on the UN SDG goals but many of the large companies have independently formulated corporate social responsibility (CSR) policies that stand apart from the SFS initiative (Vigfússon et al., 2024).

The sustainability reporting practices of the largest aquaculture companies is based on frameworks like UN Global compact aligned with the SDG and using the general requirements of the GRI standard as well as synergies with the ESG reporting. The double materiality is being considered as required by ESRS, but not fully implemented. The most recent reports have used the GRI 13 sector standard which covers the challenges facing the aquaculture and the materiality topics identified along with the associated risk assessment. Companies have often set their own policies regarding the materiality topics to explain e.g. the purpose, principles, relevant regulations and standards, targets, and responsibilities. The largest companies (Table 2) are all certified against the ASC standard although not all sites are certified, but their aim is generally to have 100% of all sites certified.

Table 2 CSR Reporting in aquaculture companies in Norway and Iceland

Companies	ASC ¹⁾	UN-SDG	ESG	GRI	CSR reporting Reports on websites checked
		Framework			
Mowi Seawater AS	87/96	x	x	x	Mowi Integrated Annual Report 2023 ¹²
SalMar ASA	70/81		x	x	Salmar Annual report 2023
Lerøy Aurora Sjø AS / Lerøy Midt Sjø	41/41	x	x	x	Lerøy Annual report 2023
Grieg Seafood	23/22	x	x	x	Grieg Seafood Integrated Annual report 2023
Nova Sea Havbruk AS	21/22	x		x	Nova Sea Sustainability report 2023
Cermaq Norway Salmon AS	19/29	x	x	x	Cermaq Sustainability report 2023
Nordlaks Havbruk AS	10/10			x	Nordlax Sustainability Report 2022
Arnarlax / Icelandic Salmon AS (Salmar)	2	x	x	x	Consolidated Annual Report 2023 ¹³
Arctic Fish (Mowi)	1	x	x	x	Reported in Mowi Integrated Annual Report 2023
Kaldvík / Ice Fish Farm	5				NA

1) number of sites ASC certified checked in April 2024/October 2024 <https://asc-aqua.org/find-a-farm/>

All the companies have Global GAP and /or BAP certification for the production and GFSI approved certification for the processing along with ISO standards in some companies. Furthermore, the large companies are leaders in the sector and partake in various sustainability initiatives see examples in **Error! Not a valid bookmark self-reference.**

¹² [Mowi Integrated Annual Report 2023](#)

¹³ [Icelandic-Salmon-AS-consolidated-statement-2023-final.pdf](#)

Table 3 Examples of initiatives, certifications and frameworks applied by companies in fisheries and aquaculture sectors in Iceland and Norway

Standards Certifications
MSC Marine Stewardship Council
GSSI Global Sustainable Seafood Initiative
ASC Aquaculture Stewardship Council
Global G.A.P. standards - integrated farm assurance solutions for the certification of e.g. aquaculture and global supply chains,
GAA GAP Global Aquaculture Alliance
BAP standard established by the Global Seafood Alliance
Organic certifications: Debio organic, KRAV, EU Org Aquac
Proterra standard – deforestation the Aquaculture Dialogue on Sustainable Soy Sourcing in Brazil
Food Safety Management System was certified to ISO 22000 standards
Environmental Management System (EMS) certified to the international ISO 14001 EMS standard
Quality Management System certified to ISO 9001 standards
Occupational Health and Safety Management System ISO 45001 standards .
FSSC 22000 is GFSI-recognized and follows the food chain category description as defined in ISO 22003-1:2022.
Global Food Safety Initiative GFSI recognise a number of certification programmes that meet the GFSI Benchmarking Requirements e.g. BRCGS/IFS -
Frameworks and initiatives
United Nations Guiding Principles on Business and Human Rights,
Science Based Targets initiative is a collaboration between CDP, the United Nations Global Compact (UNGC), World Resources Institute (WRI), and the World Wide Fund for Nature (WWF)
Sustainable Ocean Principles - organized by UN Global Compact
Together with Nature Initiative - businesses and civil society unite in support for the Together with Nature Principles for nature-based solutions.
Task Force on Climate-Related Financial Disclosure (TCFD) recommendations enable stakeholders to understand carbon-related assets and their exposures to climate-related risks, opportunities and financial impacts.
Task Force on Nature related financial disclosures TNFD
Global Biodiversity Framework, the Taskforce on Nature-related Financial Disclosures and the WWF Biodiversity Risk Filter (BRF) guidelines ¹⁰
Carbon Disclosure Project (CDP) reporting of strategy, climate, and energy accounts, with associated initiatives and improvements
SASB Sustainability Accounting Standards Board – an independent standards-setting organisation that promotes disclosure of material sustainability information to meet investor needs.
EU taxonomy aligned activities / env. obj.)
Norwegian Transparency Act The aim is to promote enterprises’ respect for fundamental human rights and decent working conditions and ensuring that consumers, organizations, trade unions, journalists and the general public have access to information. The Transparency Act is a Norwegian initiative, but similar initiatives in other European countries as well as at EU level
SFS Loftslagsvegvísir fiskeldis Loftslagsvegvísir - Fiskeldi

Table 4 is an overview of the alignment of the ESRS material topics with the reported sustainability materiality topics of aquaculture and fisheries companies which are generally based on the GRI framework and ESG and established KPIs. The new sector specific GRI 13 standard for agriculture, aquaculture and fisheries includes topics 13.3. Biodiversity and 13.4 Natural ecosystem conversion which are aligned with the ESRS E4 “Biodiversity and ecosystems” and captures the biodiversity challenges related to feed sourcing, fish health and welfare (e.g. sea lice) and the impacts of escapes on the wild salmon etc. The ESRS5 “Circular economy” will require more detailed information and data on resource use, RRM and FLW than is currently reported by companies.

Table 4 ESRS material topics and topics reported by companies in aquaculture sectors in Iceland and Norway (From Saviolidis et al., 2025)

ESRS	Topic	Subtopic	GRI 13: Agriculture, Aquaculture and Fishing Sectors 2022	ESG topics	Company Reporting Examples of topics / KPIs
ESRS E1	Climate change	Climate change adaptation Climate change mitigation Energy	13.1 Emissions GRI.3 Material Topics 2021 /13.1.1 GRI 305: Emissions /13.1.2-13.1.8 13.2 Climate adaptation and resilience GRI 3 13.2.1 GRI 201: Economic Performance 2016 /13.2.2	E1. GHG Emissions E2. Emissions Intensity E7. Environmental Operations /policies E8. Climate Oversight / Board E9. Climate Oversight / Management E10. Climate Risk Mitigation E3. Energy usage E4. Energy intensity E5. Energy mix	GHG emissions Scope 1 Scope 2 and Scope 3 GHG intensity Climate risks and opportunities Energy use, Energy intensity and scope 3 emission /Science based targets Electrical hybrid solutions /transition to renewable energy Targets: Reduction in Scope 1,2,3 intensity
ESRS E2	Pollution	Pollution of air Pollution of water Pollution of soil Pollution of living organisms and food resources Substances of concern Substances of very high concern Microplastics	13.5 Soil health 13.6 Pesticides use		N/A N/A (justified by strict regulation when it comes to undesirable substances in feed). Awareness of plastic material contributing to pollution of the ocean – collecting fishing gear and nets etc. Beach cleaning
ESRS E3	Water and marine resources	Water Water consumption Water withdrawals Water discharges Water discharges in the oceans	113.7 Water use and effluents GRI 303: Water and effluents 2018 13.7.2 Interactions with water as a shared resource 13.7.3Management of water discharge-related impacts 13.7.4 Water withdrawal 13.7.5Water discharge	E6 Water usage	Water use and recycling Freshwater use Use of RAS (Recirculation Aquaculture System) technology) for smolt

		Marine resources Extraction and use of marine resources	13.7.6 Water consumption See Circular economy 13.3.6 and 13.3.7		Supply of fish Harvest volumes- ASC /MSC certification Efficiency in use of marine raw materials Increasing share of VAP – strengthen processing capacity – long term partnerships with third parties - FCR (economic FCR, biological FCR) Marine sources in feed: Fish Dependency Ratio for fish meal (FFDRm) and for fish oil (FFDRo).
ESRS E4	Biodiversity and ecosystems	<p>Direct impact drivers of biodiversity loss</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Climate Change Land-use change, fresh water-use change and sea-use change Direct exploitation Invasive alien species Pollution Others <p>Impacts on the state of species</p> <p>Impacts on the extent and condition of ecosystems</p> <p>Impacts and dependencies on ecosystem services</p>	<p>13.3 Biodiversity GRI 3 Material topic</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Describe the approach to preventing and managing escapes of farmed aquatic organisms. <p>GRI 304: Biodiversity 2016</p> <p>13.3.2 Operational sites owned, leased, managed in, or adjacent to, protected areas and areas of high biodiversity value outside protected areas</p> <p>13.3.3 Significant impacts of activities, products and services on biodiversity</p> <p>13.3.4 Habitats protected or restored</p> <p>13.3.5 IUCN Red List species and national conservation list species with habitats in areas affected by operations</p> <p>13.4 Natural ecosystem conversion</p> <p>13.4.1. Describe policies or commitments to reduce or eliminate natural ecosystem conversion, including target and cut-off dates, for the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - the organization's own production; sourcing of terrestrial animal and fish feed;- products sourced by the organization for aggregation, processing, or trade. - Describe how the organization ensures that its suppliers comply with its natural ecosystem conversion policies and commitments, including through sourcing policies and contracts. 		<p>Protected areas, Interaction with wildlife, (birds, marine mammals) Ghost fishing, impacts on IUCN red listed species</p> <p>Healthy ocean -Fish health and welfare: survival rate at sea, use of antibiotics, sea lice treatments, use of hydrogen peroxide,</p> <p>Escape incidence (Target: zero escape)</p> <p>Sourcing of sustainable feed ingredients / linked to traceability</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • use of fish in feed - MSC • use of soy - ProTerra (deforestation) • Innovation novel feed <p>Certifications</p> <p>Protected areas</p> <p>Area management: Optimize the production efficiency, animal welfare, and ecological sustainability e.g. Precision farming and data driver decision support (Grieg)</p> <p>-Seabed monitoring (inorganic and organic loading, e.g. nitrogen, carbon and phosphorous), estimated through the quantities of uneaten feed and the salmon's faecal matter.</p> <p>-Fallow time between production cycles</p> <p>-Wastewater management and monitoring</p>

			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Report the organization's participation in multi-stakeholder, landscape, or sectoral initiatives intended to reduce or eliminate natural ecosystem conversion. - Describe the tools and systems used to monitor natural ecosystem conversion in the organization's activities, supply chain, and sourcing locations 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Sustainable feed: Requirements on raw material in feed (traceability, certified raw material (e.g. MSC, Proterra) Code of Conduct for feed suppliers
ESRS E5	Circular economy	<p>Resources inflows, including resource use</p> <p>Resource outflows related to products and services</p>	<p>13.3.6 For each species of aquatic organisms produced, report:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - species scientific name; - volume in metric tons; - farming methods; - production site. <p>For juvenile seeds stocks captured in the wild that are used as input to aquaculture production, report: - species scientific name; - volume in metric tons; - fishing methods; - locations of origin; - stock status, including the stock status assessments or systems used.</p> <p>13.3.7 Report the use of fishing products in feed, including the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - species scientific name; - whether the whole fish or fish waste (trimmings, offcuts, and offal) is used; - locations of origin; - stock status, including the stock status assessments or systems used. <p>For each species of aquatic organisms caught or harvested, including non-target species, report: - species scientific name; - volume in metric tons; - fishing methods; - locations of origin; - stock status, including the stock status assessments or systems used</p> <p>13.9 Food security FLW GRI 3: Material Topics 2021. Food loss</p> <p>13.9.1 Management of material topics:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Describe the effectiveness of actions and programs on food security at local, regional, national, or global levels. -Report partnerships which the organization is part of that address food 	<p>Optimisation and enhanced efficiency in the supply chain</p> <p>Fish raw material (catch weight, processed weight etc.)</p> <p>Fish utilization / efficiency /share of secondary processing</p> <p>RRM fish meal, fish oil /feed / value added products (Target 0% food waste)</p> <p>Ex. Policy on circular economy and responsible waste management</p> <p>Size of salmon stocked to net pens (grams per individual)</p> <p>Salmon stock in ocean net pens at start of year (Tonnes)</p> <p>Stocking of juveniles (Tonnes) Harvest (Tonnes) Feed use (Tonnes) LWE for human consumption</p> <p>FCR, (efficient feed utilisation)</p> <p>Ex. Salmar -increase the use of trimmings and by-products in the feed /increase inclusion of novel feed ingredients</p> <p>Ex. Nordlaks:Havbruk – use of RRM for oil and hydrolysates for humans and animals.</p> <p>Documenting waste / organic waste (silage and sludge) /100 % of the organic waste to recycling / biogas plants and fuel oil. -used to generate electricity, heat, fuel, and fertilizer.</p> <p>Utilize 100 % of the fish</p> <p>RRM fish meal, fish oil /feed</p> <p>FLW biological waste (silage, sludge) /</p> <p>Ex. Leroy: In wild catch segment - the target is to preserve residual raw material and increase the production of meal, oil, and ensilage. the vessel Kongsfjord producing silage from 2020 and</p>

		<p>security, including engagement with governments. -Describe policies or commitments to address food loss in the supply chain. 13.9.2 Report the total weight of food loss in metric tons and the food loss percentage, by the organization’s main products or product category, and describe the methodology used for this calculation.</p>		<p>optimization of oil and meal production on other vessels. The production has increased and is utilized as an ingredient in feed for the farming division.</p> <p>Ex. Icelandic fisheries companies-emphasise full utilisation of all raw material landed – e.g. head and backbone dried, liver and roe delivered for value added products.</p> <p>Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) has the potential of circular use of nutrient in the ocean. - kelp and mussels as a possible method for removing organic and inorganic loading from the sea and seabed / develop new ingredients for human consumption or feed and new species in aquaculture (e.g. Leroy /Ocean Forest AS; MOWI, Kelp Crofting & Univ. Sterling)</p> <p>Waste management, Recycled materials Waste stream mapping – Target: Zero waste to landfill Packaging material, Plastics (reduce use of EPS packaging / alternative packaging) Recycling of fishing gear/aquaculture equipment e.g. pipes, tanks, pumps cage collars etc), Beach cleaning</p>		
ESRS S1	Own workforce	<p>Waste</p>	<p>13.8 Waste GRI 306: Waste 2020 13.8.2 Waste generation and significant waste-related impacts 13.8.3 Management of significant waste-related impacts 13.8.4 Waste generated 13.8.5 Waste diverted from disposal 13.8.6 Waste directed to disposal</p>	<p>Working conditions -Secure employment -Working time -Adequate wages -Social dialogue -Freedom of association, the existence of works councils and the information, consultation and participation rights of workers -Collective bargaining, including rate of workers covered by collective agreements -Work-life balance -Health and safety</p>	<p>13.15 Non-discrimination and equal opportunity 13.16 Forced or compulsory labor 13.17 Child labor 13.18 Freedom of association and collective bargaining 13.20 Employment practices 13.21 Living income and living wage 13.22 Economic inclusion 13.19 Occupational health and safety</p> <p>S1. CEO Pay Ratio S2. Gender Pay Ratio S3. Employee Turnover S4. Gender Diversity S5. Temporary Worker Ratio S6. Non-Discrimination S7. Injury Rate</p> <p>S9. Child & Forced Labor</p>	<p>Working conditions, Equal treatment</p> <p>Injuries and absentees OHS management systems OHS health service Work training on OHS Whistle blowing</p>

ESRS S2	Workers in the value chain	Working conditions Equal treatment and opportunities for all Other work-related rights			Workers in the value chain Transparency Act report (Norway) The aim is to promote enterprises' respect for fundamental human rights and decent working conditions and ensuring that consumers, organizations, trade unions, journalists and the public have access to information. KPI Sickness absence rate
ESRS S3	Affected communities	Communities' economic, social and cultural rights Communities' civil and political rights Rights of indigenous peoples	13.12 Local communities 13.13 Land and resource rights 13.14 Rights of indigenous peoples	S10. Human Rights	Community Resilience Rights of indigenous peoples,
ESRS S4	Consumers and end-users	Information-related impacts for consumers and/or end-users Personal safety of consumers and/or end-users Social inclusion of consumers and/or end-users	13.10 Food safety	S8. Global Health & Safety	Sustainable food: carbon emission per tonn / high quality products Health and safety of consumers Non-compliances with food safety regulations
ESRS G1	Business conduct	Corporate culture Protection of whistle-blowers Animal welfare Political engagement and lobbying activities Management of relationships with suppliers including payment practices Corruption and bribery	13.11 Animal health and welfare 13.24 Public policy 13.23 Supply chain traceability 13.25 Anti-competitive behavior 13.26 Anti-corruption	G1. Board Diversity G2. Board Independence G3. Incentivized Pay G8. ESG Reporting G9. Disclosure Practices G10. External Assurance G4. Collective Bargaining G5. Supplier Code of Conduct G7. Data Privacy G6. Ethics & Anti-Corruption	Fish health and welfare. Fish mortality / fish survival rate, Vaccination, Antibiotic use, Sea lice management, etc, Political engagement Code of conduct for suppliers

3.2 GOVERNANCE AND POLICY RELATED TO CE

The implementation of circular economy (CE) principles has been facilitated by top-down actions by policy makers taking lead or as bottom-up organizational innovation (Ruggieri et al., 2016). In 2015, the European Commission adopted the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP)¹⁴ to accelerate EU's transition towards a circular economy. The action plan supports transition of linear material flows to become circular with the aims of reducing resource use, creating more efficient processes, addressing the region's material dependency, and improving its long-term competitiveness [EC,2020]¹⁵. The CEAP integrates several of the Commission's directives, policy frameworks and initiatives to enhance sustainability (e.g., Farm-to-Fork, Green Deal, the sustainable products policy framework, and waste framework directive (WFD)¹⁶. Furthermore, the EU's environmental policies are designed to speed up the transition to a sustainable, innovative and circular economy, where biodiversity is protected, valued and restored and environment-related health risks are minimised. They aim to enhance the EU's resilience and to decouple growth from resource use¹⁷.

It is important to include also food systems and food policies when considering relevant policies for the blue bioeconomy especially when focusing on the primary sectors of fisheries and aquaculture whose primary product is fish. Fish is food and constitutes a source of important nutrients for many people around the world (Boyd et al., 2022). Food relates to several important topics beyond environmental impacts and resource efficiency which are the primary focus of circular economy policies, such as health and nutrition, food security, food safety and quality. Shaping policy in such a way that it can integrate these different policy domains that are integral to increasing the sustainability of food systems is crucial (Galli et al., 2020). Similarly, food policy also needs to integrate land and marine systems in policy making as seafood tends to be underrepresented and many opportunities exist to improve utilization.

A further consideration is the importance of including social dimensions in policy making for the blue bioeconomy and circularity (Axon & Collier, 2022). Though the emphasis has been mostly on environmental impacts and aspects, seafood sectors constitute major sources of income for many countries. The governance of the seafood industry is regulated through a combination of public and private governance arrangements, including public regulation, private certification schemes, and self-regulation involving many actors including the state, private businesses, and society (Vince and Hayward, 2017, Ólafsdóttir et al., 2019, Luthman et al., 2019, Rector et al.,2024). In Iceland and Norway these sectors are major export sectors and thus important to the national economy.

A fisheries management system has been in place for decades in both countries with several common aspects including the provision of scientific stock assessments and a Total Allowable Catch (TAC) for commercial stocks to maximize utilisation without the risk of overfishing. At the same time, the system of Individually Transferable Quotas (ITQs) has led to much consolidation and concentration of fishing companies in both countries which has been a cause of social discontent due to regional development issues and perceived injustice (Gunnlaugsson & Valtýsson, 2022). In Iceland, aquaculture has been seen as a sector that can promote regional development where fishing has disappeared from certain coastal areas in recent years. However, the sector has also faced resistance from locals in some regions as well due to known environmental impacts such as impact on wild salmon populations from escapes. Both industries face various challenges in terms of social acceptance and

¹⁴ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/EN/legal-content/glossary/circular-economy.html>

¹⁵ https://environment.ec.europa.eu/strategy/circular-economy-action-plan_en

¹⁶ Waste Framework Directive (Commission Decision, 2011/753/EU, EU 2019)

¹⁷ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=LEGISSUM:environment>

perceptions and policy has been slow to address these (Bjørkan & Eilertsen, 2020; Holm et al., 2015, Osmundsen and Olsen, 2017).

The following table lists some of the key policies and strategies relevant to the bioeconomy that have been formulated at international, regional and national levels. This list is not exhaustive and as mentioned above several topics such as health and nutrition and social equity considerations would need to be better integrated for a blue bioeconomy to achieve broader sustainability goals than those generally defined under circular economy strategies.

Table 5 Key policies and strategies relevant to the bioeconomy

Region	Document (policy, strategy, report)	Year	Relation to bioeconomy
International	Global Bioeconomy Assessment: Coordinated Efforts of Policy, Innovation, and Sustainability for a Greener Future (UNEP)	2024	Overview of definitions, tracing the history and policy development worldwide of the bioeconomy. Makes limited reference to seafood sectors.
	Realising the circular bioeconomy (OECD)	2018	Outlines some of the synergies between circular economy policies and bioeconomic policies as well as the various misalignments in policy thereof.
European	Circular Economy Action Plan (COM)	2020	Outlines the European Commission's strategy for achieving circularity aims and listing all the relevant EU initiatives and regulations and key product value chains where more circularity is crucial including food, water and nutrients, packaging and plastics.
Nordic	Nordic Bioeconomy Programme: 15 Action Points for Sustainable Change ((NCM)	2018	Outlines an integrated policy programme for the bioeconomy in the Nordic region with fifteen actions points to reach common principles.
	Future Opportunities for Bioeconomy Focus on the West Nordic Region (NCM)	2015	Focuses on Iceland, the Faroe Islands and Greenland and bioeconomic resource exploitation opportunities.
	Resilience in the blue bioeconomy: What can COVID-19 teach the Arctic about the impact of crises on value chains? (NCM)	2021	Short outline of the way blue value chains adapted to the Covid-19 pandemic and how policy can support adaptation and resilience in future crises.
Norway	National Bioeconomy Strategy (MTIF)	2016	Comprehensive strategy document - outlines Norway's vision for a sustainable bioeconomy, including specific goals and actions related to the use of forest and marine resources, biotechnology, and other sectors.
	Ocean Strategy (MTIF)	2021	The Norwegian Government's ocean and ocean industries strategy – outlines the most important initiatives nationally and internationally regarding Norway's ocean policy.
	Sustainable forestry (NIBIO)	2021	Compilation of data on the development and status of Norwegian forests

	Green alliance between Norway and the EU for climate action and the green transition (OPM)	2023	Outlines goals and strategies for reducing GHG emissions and promoting renewable energy production, including measures to promote the use of bioenergy and other forms of renewable energy
	Strategy for Green Competitiveness (MCI)	2017	Outlines goals and strategies for promoting sustainable economic growth and competitiveness, including measures to promote the development of a sustainable bioeconomy
	Marine Biodiversity Strategy (NMCE, 2022a)	2022	Outlines goals and strategies for the conservation and sustainable use of Norway's marine biodiversity, including measures to protect and restore marine ecosystems and promote sustainable fishing practices
	Norwegian Plastics Strategy (NMCE, 2022b)	2022	Comprehensive strategy with measures to reduce plastic litter and plastic pollution including measures targeting plastic across its entire lifecycle.
Iceland	Climate action plan	2020	Outlines 48 actions for Iceland to meet its Paris Agreement targets for 2030 and carbon neutrality before 2040.
	National policy on waste reduction "Saman gegn sóun" (EA)	2016-2027	Advancing the circular economy with better resource utilization and increased education and communication on waste reduction actions. The policy has tackled a different sector each year starting with meat and fish by-products in its first year.
	Iceland's Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change (MENR)	2021	Outlines the Icelandic government's response and adaptation measures to climate risks which were previously identified by the Icelandic Climate Council (an independent body of experts with an advisory role to the government). Includes specific goals concerning fisheries and marine farming in connection to the identified risk of ocean acidification and warming.
	Fisheries Management System*		
	Iceland's Policy on Matters Concerning the Arctic Region (MFAI)	2021	Outlines various policies related to arctic issues including protection of the arctic marine environment, responsible fisheries policy and climate change mitigation and adaptation measures

* Iceland does not have a comprehensive ocean strategy for the different marine and coastal industries like Norway, but the fisheries management system is in place and a policy on aquaculture

3.3 CHALLENGES, LEVERAGE POINTS, POLICY TOOLS AND ROLE OF ACTORS

SUSTAINABILITY CHALLENGES AND CIRCULARITY APPROACHES

The sustainability challenges facing seafood business are multidimensional and require the attention of all stakeholders, policy makers, industries and citizens. The challenges include environmental threats (climate change, marine debris, resources depletion), social development (worker rights, consumer’s awareness) or economic growth (market and nonmarket goods and services, global competitiveness) (Ruiz-Salomon et al., 2020). The main environmental challenges are associated with the use of fossil fuel in harvesting operations of fisheries and on farm activities in agriculture (use of fuel, pesticides and fertilizers) when producing crop e.g. soy as feed ingredients for aquaculture. Challenges related to climate change are in focus, but there is also a need to consider impacts on ecosystems and biodiversity, as well as social and economic aspects and governance, and policy implications.

Figure 4 is a conceptual framework for the blue bioeconomy to visualise the biomaterial flow (bluegreen) from harvesting of biomass from aquaculture and fisheries through processing to final products in market and the identified circularity pathways (green).

Figure 4 Conceptual framework (adapted from Carus, 2017) for the circular blue bioeconomy

Although full utilisation of the raw material and value-added products have been motivated in the seafood industries, there are still significant amounts of under-utilized rest raw materials (RRM), such as heads, skins, viscera, and food loss and waste (FLW) occurring in the demersal fisheries supply chains in Iceland and Norway (Strand et al., 2024; Myhre et al., 2023). Better use of RRM can motivate new circular business models on top of the core activities of the companies for example collagen from fish skin, fish oil, ingredients for value added products for human consumption, food supplements and feed and fertilizers or bioenergy from remaining biowaste.

Norway has invested in technology and infrastructure for the responsible recycling of aquaculture nets and other plastic waste from fisheries while both countries are exploring the potential of biorefineries to transform fish processing waste into high-value products, reducing waste and enhancing resource efficiency (Strand et al., 2024). The SMARTCHAIN project has focused on selected cases on sustainability and circularity improvements in fisheries and aquaculture supply chains including automation and efficiency in preprocessing using robots,

collagen/gelatin production from fish skins (herring and salmon) in collaboration with the industry partner Seagarden and optimisation / simulation models for improved logistics and decision making in collaboration with the seafood company BRIM.

ROLE OF ACTORS

The role of the private sector in food system transitions in general is highly contested (Zeppenfeldt et al., 2024) in part because the growing concentration of food business translates in increased influence over public policy and governance (Clapp, 2021). Such influence need not be detrimental to sustainability goals but does threaten the proper function of markets by compromising competition and thus can have some outsized influence on various issues such as the variety of crops grown, working conditions, variety of products available in grocery stores among other things (Clapp, 2021). In many ways the private sector's influence – and especially that of large transnational firms - is like a double edged sword; the increased power and influence of large corporate actors means that they have outsized influence in shaping innovation trends and sustainable business practices which cascade through the private sector in larger and smaller companies. On the other hand, the necessary breakthrough innovations needed for increasing sustainability may be hampered by small number of large firms investing in more status quo research and development (Zeppenfeldt et al., 2024). Increased sustainability and circularity demand more collaborations and partnerships as no single company wants to bear the cost for improved practices. However, this emphasis on partnerships and collaboration may undermine competition law and the proper function of markets.

The role of the government thus becomes important with setting tighter regulations and policies that encourage sustainability and circularity in order to level the playing field encouraging competition on equal grounds but also to drive the private sector beyond gains in the short term (increased sales and growth) to important long-term goals (sustainability, circularity) (Dauvergne & Lister, 2012). Incentives and consistent ambitious policy frameworks can also further encourage the adoption of more sustainable business practices. In the fishing industry in Iceland for example increased sustainability has been in many ways the result of setting scientifically imposed limits to harvesting (Total Allowable Catch TAC) which has arguably encouraged increased utilization in the sector (Saviolidis et al., 2020). At the same time the market-based approach (Individually Transferrable Quota (ITQ) system) has increased vertical integration and concentration which has led to various other issues to do with rural development, fewer job opportunities in the sector and outsized influence in the public policy sphere (Nielsen et al., 2018).

The role of civil society whether through individuals (such as public intellectuals or activists) or through Not-for-Profit Organizations (NGOs) with an emphasis on environmental protection and sustainable development issues is to scrutinize both the private and public sectors on their policies and practices. From both a global governance perspective and a national perspective, increasing the participation of NGOs in public policy forums is crucial to counterbalancing the outsized influence of the private sector in policy making. It is, however, equally important to garner independent scientific assessment in public debates so that different actors can find a common ground to build upon when debating solutions to sustainability and circularity (Clapp, 2021).

BARRIERS TO TRANSITIONING TOWARDS SUSTAINABILITY AND CIRCULARITY

Various barriers have been identified to implementing circular business aimed at transitioning to circular blue bioeconomy (CBE), such as policies and regulations, small market size of bio-based markets and higher costs compared to the linear model (Stegmann et al., 2020). For seafood, logistical challenges can hinder the efficient utilisation of seafood rest raw materials and transition to a circular economy in seafood supply chains can be complex and requires communication, education, and engagement with stakeholders to increase awareness and acceptance (Cooney et al., 2023). Furthermore, several recent papers on the key challenges identified for circularity in the bioeconomy and blue bioeconomy have been published and this is detailed further in a forthcoming manuscript for publication.

Our results from in-depth interviews and focus groups with stakeholders in Iceland and Norway revealed the barriers and the challenges involved in transforming the fisheries and aquaculture food supply systems towards more sustainable and circular bioeconomic systems. The findings on drivers and barriers were categorised according to key themes: regulatory, resource, market and social (Table 6). Resource barriers were most often mentioned by the interviewees in both countries (Saviolidis et al., 2023). These institutional barriers along with literature sources are synthesized further in the next chapter.

Table 6 Summary and selected findings from stakeholder interviews on the perception of challenges and barriers in Iceland and Norway (Source: SMARTCHAIN Deliverable 3.2. Saviolidis et al. 2023)

Iceland	Norway
Resource (53%)¹⁾: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for holistic mapping of waste streams (quantities and content) • Raw material issues: volume, price, competition for resources • Infrastructure: waste management and wastewater management • Energy supply issues 	Resource (61%): <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Climate risks: warming waters, extreme weather • Raw material issues: export of unprocessed fish • Need for holistic approach: avoid tunnel vision; local vs global
Regulatory (35%) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of institutional capacity • Need for common standards and metrics. • Need for policy integration. • Need for long term policy. 	Regulatory (14%) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Taxation • Licences for aquaculture • EU policy issues: agri by products
Social (7%) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to change • Negative public discourse 	Social (12%) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • License to operate • Negative public discourse
Market (5%) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Need for partnerships and collaboration. • Need for integration 	Market (13%) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consumer perceptions • Markets not ready

1) % is the frequency of topic mentioned by interviewees

SYNTHESIS OF CHALLENGES, LEVERAGE POINTS, POLICY TOOLS AND ROLE OF ACTORS

For structuring our results on key challenges and multistakeholder perspectives of key barriers to a more sustainable and circular blue bioeconomy, we apply the four broad categories of institutional barriers: a) social, b) market, c) resource and d) regulatory (Saviolidis et al., 2024, SMARTCHAIN D3.2). Additionally, a category of organisational representation is acknowledged to include e.g. “sectoral routines and structure” in line with Gottinger et al. (2020). Based on systematic literature review with a focus on wood-based and agriculture sectors, six categories of Circular Bio-Economy (CBE) transition barriers were identified: a) policy and regulation, b) technology and materials, c) market and investment conditions, d) social acceptance, e) knowledge and networks, and g) sectoral routines and structures. They concluded that more studies focusing on regional and national particularities are needed (Gottinger et al., 2020). Furthermore, a more detailed categorisation and a framework of drivers and barriers for the implementation of circularity was reported by Tura et al. (2019) including seven distinct areas: environmental, economic, social, political and institutional, technological and informational, supply chain, and opportunities for RRM derived products in global markets with high organizational factors.

The key challenges identified and barriers to a more sustainable and circular blue bioeconomy are analysed according to five broad categories of institutional barriers:

- social
- market
- resource
- regulatory

To analyse further the findings from the SMARTCHAIN research on the key challenges and integrating the implications for policy and management options, we followed an analytical framework of policy tool categorisation applied by Saviolidis et al. (2020). The policy tool categorizing is based on Galli et al.’s (2020) typology of five broad food policy categories. Figure 5 presents an overview and brief explanation of each category.

Figure 5 Classification of policy tools with examples. Source: Adapted from Saviolidis et al. (2020), based on Galli et al. (2020)

Inspired by Medows (1999) we apply the definition of leverage points as places to intervene in the system for example by e.g. technical advance or social demand which in system dynamics is referred to as self-organization. The leverage is understanding the limitation of the physical structure and refraining from fluctuations or expansion that strain its capacity.

Table 7 summarises the key challenges and leverage points for enhanced sustainability with a focus on better use of RRM and minimizing FLW in the seafood value chain This is based on literature and earlier research in SMARTCHAIN.

The leverage points identified here are categorised according to resource, social, market and regulatory challenges and include for example *sectoral routines and structure, institutional, technological, informational and supply chain solutions.*

Table 7 Challenges, leverage points, policy tools and key actors responsible for motivating enhanced sustainability and circular bioeconomy in fisheries and aquaculture value chains in Iceland and Norway (further information “notes” listed below)

Challenges	Leverage points (solutions)	Policy tool	Role / Responsibility
Resource			
<i>Discards, FLW and RRM not utilised</i>	<i>Establish incentives to enhance RRM utilisation and minimise FLW Interventions on board vessels to limit losses/discards and enhance quality of RRM by ensuring adequate storage facilities and implement technologies to preserve and monitor quality.</i>	<i>Direct regulations</i>	<i>Government</i>
<i>Lacking data on volumes of RRM and FLW</i> Note 1)	<i>Mandate procedures for reporting available volumes of RRM and FLW in fisheries</i>	<i>Direct regulations</i>	<i>Government</i>
<i>Transparency of data on FLW and RRM</i> Note 2)	<i>Provide transparent data on available volumes and information on RRM in fisheries and processing to facilitate decision making, and apply the data further for developing optimisation and simulation models for improved decision making for enhanced circularity and resource utilisation and reduce waste in the seafood supply chain</i>	<i>Knowledge based</i> <i>Strategic</i>	<i>Industry</i>
<i>Regulatory barriers to the use of FLW and RRM</i> Note 3)	<i>Influence changes to the regulation on risk and food safety issue Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009(2009) Reduce waste and enhance resource utilisation for value added products (food and feed)</i>	<i>Direct regulations</i>	<i>Government</i>
<i>Lacking efficiency in preprocessing</i>	<i>Developing innovative technologies (e.g. robots) for improved handling, chilling (preserving) and sorting according to quality in preprocessing to enhance efficiency, preserve quality including RRM and minimise loss (R&D - innovation)</i>	<i>Knowledge based</i>	<i>Industry actors</i>
<i>Lacking communication and transparency of information flow between supply chain steps</i>	<i>Facilitate decision making through transparent information sharing between the fishing fleet, seafood processors and/or the marine ingredient sector to enhance resource utilization and close resource loops through better management of supply and demand.</i>	<i>Strategic</i> <i>Market</i>	<i>Industry (national and global industry actors)</i>
<i>RRM traceability is lacking</i>	<i>Implement improved traceability: Provide accurate and transparent information and data on quantities of RRM in the seafood industry to inform potential users of the availability of RRM for e.g. value-added products. Blockchain could facilitate the traceability procedures</i>	<i>Direct regulations</i> <i>Market</i>	<i>Government</i> <i>Industry</i>
<i>Lacking infrastructure, technology and knowledge</i>	<i>Enhance the capacity and infrastructure to utilize RRM for value creation and close resource loops (sludge – biogas)</i>	<i>Strategic</i>	<i>Government</i>

<i>Limitation of financial capacity - structural barriers and lack of skilled employees</i>	<i>Enhance upscaling and value-added processing of RRM in the seafood industry (e.g. fish skin for collagen production, blood in aquaculture etc.).</i> Training, Facilitate employment of foreign experts	<i>Direct regulations</i> <i>Market Knowledge based</i>	<i>Government</i> <i>Industry</i>
<i>Alternative packaging needed for perishable products like seafood</i> Note 4	<i>Phase out plastic packaging and implement alternative materials with comparable properties (UNEP https://www.unep.org/inc-plastic-pollution)</i>	<i>Direct regulations</i> <i>Strategic</i>	<i>Government</i> <i>Industry</i>
<i>Energy use – Fossil fuels</i> Climate change impact (warming oceans, acidification) Note 5)	<i>Shift towards energy efficiency and alternative fuels,</i> Optimise harvesting and processing Fuel intensity Note 6)		<i>Industry</i> <i>Government</i>
<i>Logistical challenges in collection of RRM - export orientation</i>	<i>Create incentives for secondary production and reduce the export of whole fish which compromises the availability of rest raw material for value added products</i> <i>Government to lobby for reducing tariff to EU on VAP (NO)</i>	<i>Strategic</i>	<i>Food value chain</i> <i>Government</i>
<i>Fishing gear impact on biodiversity loss and enhanced carbon emission</i>	<i>Need for policy to avoid exclusive focus on avoided atmospheric emissions, and consider the trawling-induced increases in DIC (dissolved inorganic carbon) in seawater Note 7)</i>	<i>Direct regulations</i>	<i>Government</i>
<i>Environmental impact of feed</i> Note 8)	Sourcing policy of feed ingredients Biodiversity loss - Deforestation soy for feed/ Climate change impact / Carbon emission - Use of fertilisers, pesticides in agriculture / fuel use in fisheries	<i>Strategic</i>	<i>Industry</i>
<i>Feed for aquaculture</i>	<i>Ongoing research on alternative sustainable feed (competition for RRM with the value added industry e.g. fish oil)</i>	<i>Knowledge based</i> <i>Strategic</i>	<i>Industry actors</i>
<i>Waste</i> Note 9)	More effective waste management strategy would need to include waste minimization, characterizing the waste, and waste recycling	<i>Strategic</i> <i>Direct regulations</i>	<i>Industry</i> <i>Government</i>
<i>Wastewater</i>	Infrastructure needed	<i>Direct regulations</i>	<i>Industry</i> <i>Government</i>
Metrics to assess BCE transition Note 10)	<i>Establish relevant indicators to assess sustainability and performance of circular approaches - life cycle assessment</i>	<i>Knowledge based</i>	<i>Government</i> <i>Industry – Food value chain</i> <i>NGO</i>

Social			
<i>Negative public discourse</i>	<i>Enhance knowledge and education about the industry</i> Emphasis on aquaculture as an important protein source with less environmental impact compared to animal livestock production in general. Policy on less meat and enhanced fish consumption to fulfill protein demand	Knowledge based Governance	Industry – Food value chain Government
<i>Licence to operate</i>	<i>Enhance social acceptance:</i> Social and financial benefits of the communities e.g. employment opportunities but there are various challenges related to water resource protection, animal welfare concerns, and opposition from NGOs and protesters. <i>Support a transparent legal and administrative framework of the industry and consider the social acceptance</i>	Knowledge based Governance	Industry – Food value chain Government
<i>Resistance to change</i>	<i>Enhance transparency of operations</i> The fisheries industries structure and governance has impacted their reluctance to change e.g. they have been slow to invest in IT which hinders their ability to increase transparency in their operations.	Strategic Governance	Industry – Food value chain Government NGOs
<i>Lack of an overall strategic direction by the authorities</i>	<i>Establish a long-term strategic vision from the authorities.</i> Lack of <i>strategic direction</i> hampers strategy implementation in the industry e.g. regarding the allocation of limited energy resources	Governance	Government
Market			
<i>Need for more collaboration</i>	<i>Create separate entities in charge of collaboration efforts</i> to secure enough raw material for value added production and for the feed industry, as obtaining new raw materials and upscaling ingredients is challenging Competition between companies hinders collaboration Vertical integration / mergers and acquisitions - Building trust, more collaboration – partnerships – supply chain management	Market based Strategic	Industry -Food value chain
<i>Consumer perceptions</i>	<i>Communicate to consumers about the industries' efforts towards sustainability</i> and motivate discussion and understanding on the trade offs involved in increasing sustainability	Market based	Industry – Food value chain
<i>Market readiness level low</i>	<i>Establish long term strategy to support innovation and enhance more sustainable production</i> Small market and higher cost for value added biobased products Municipalities and governments are slow to fulfil their sustainability commitments, making it an expensive risk for companies to invest in more sustainable production methods	Market based	Government Food value chain
<i>Market access and geopolitical tensions</i>	<i>Establish long term strategy to cope with uncertainties</i>	Strategic	Government

	Longer delivery times and increased transportation costs, fluctuating prices and uncertainty in the market, political tensions between Russia, the EU, and NATO		Industry – food value chain
Regulatory			
Biological challenges in aquaculture	Revision of regulations to minimise the biological challenges in aquaculture including escapes, salmon lice and treatments, eutrophication in areas below cages and impact on ecosystem, fish health and welfare. These issues are controlled by regulations (e.g. MAB and Traffic light system etc.) and linked to licensing Motivate alternative farming methods, land based, closed systems, offshore, IMTA.	<i>Direct regulations</i> <i>Strategic</i>	<i>Government</i> Industry
Biological challenges in fisheries – declining fish stocks Note 11	TAC, Fisheries management - more research needed ITQ / ecosystem-based approach	<i>Direct regulations</i>	<i>Government</i>
<i>Lack of institutional capacity</i>	<i>Enhance knowledge, transparency and avoid conflicts of interest when setting regulations for the industries.</i> Lack of knowledge among policymakers, leading to diffused effort and inadequate supervision of the industry. Administrative capacity has not been growing fast enough compared to the industry's pace of growth (IS)	<i>Knowledge based</i> <i>Strategic</i>	Government
<i>Taxation</i>	Resource rent, Carbon tax Challenge for the industry – less capacity to invest in R&D	<i>Direct regulations</i> <i>Strategic</i>	Government
Need for holistic approach	<i>Holistic and long-term approach to sustainability – avoid tunnel vision</i>	Strategic Governance	Government Industry
Policy integration	<i>Food system approach</i> needed so policies are aligned towards sustainability goals (e.g. agriculture, fisheries, aquaculture, environment, food, public health, social)	Strategic	Government

Notes to Table 4

- 1) **Better use of RRM:** Earlier findings from SMARTCHAIN research suggest that regulatory interventions during harvest and improved RRM traceability could improve the use of RRM in fisheries supply chains. Information sharing between the fishing fleet, seafood processors and the marine ingredient sector could improve resource utilization through better management of supply and demand (Strand et al., 2024). One of the main issues regarding resource barriers is that the seafood industry is export-orientated compromising availability of rest raw material and thus has not built-up capacity to utilize RRM and close resource loops (Myhre et al., 2023).
- 2) **Lack of data:** In our earlier SMARTCHAIN research the lack of data on quantities of RRM and FLW in the seafood industry was evident in both countries. In general, there is a knowledge gap in literature related to FLW quantification from the seafood sector in the Nordic countries (Strand et al., 2024; Saviolidis et al., 2024; SMARTCHAIN Deliverables 1.1&1.2, 1.3,1.4). The *data gap on resource use* is a prevalent issue pointing to a lack of transparency of information flow between supply chain stages which prevents decision making in general and influences the capacity to perform life cycle impact assessments of products.
- 3) In the context of *regulatory barriers* to the use of FLW and RRM in the fisheries and aquaculture sectors, the Regulation (EC) No 1069/2009(2009) requires risk categorization to determine the applications. For seafood processing the low-risk RRM can potentially be used for value added biobased products for human consumption, food supplements, pharmaceuticals and feed ingredients. Recycling of sludge and self-dead fish from primary production are defined as high risk and can be used to produce fertilizers for agriculture and energy (biogas) through silage (acid hydrolysis) processing and preserving, while diseased fish and food waste from retail and consumption ends up in incineration or landfill (Strand et al., 2024; Cooney et al., 2023; Egelyng et al., 2018; Myhre et al., 2023).
- 4) **Packaging and packaging waste COM (2024):** COM (2024). *Revision of Directive 94/62/EC on Packaging and Packaging Waste (REFIT)*. In "A European Green Deal". Accessed July 8, 2024 at: [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-a-european-green-deal/file-revision-of-packaging-and-packaging-waste-directive-\(refit\)](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-a-european-green-deal/file-revision-of-packaging-and-packaging-waste-directive-(refit))
- 5) **Use of fossil fuels -Climate change impacts** - For seafood products it is well documented based on LCA studies that the main climate change impacts originate from the use of fossil fuels in catching operations in fisheries (Eyjólfsson et al, 2002; Thrane, 2006). The emphasis in fisheries has been on limiting the use of fossil fuels and mitigation efforts have been on new vessels, more energy efficiency and alternative fuels. *Transport (trucking, international aviation and shipping):* The detail of the downstream impacts such as food distribution network and consumption patterns should not be overlooked, and notably there are significant climate impacts of long-distance air transport to markets for seafood products (Ziegler et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2021).
- 6) **Fuel intensity:** A recent study showed that a variation in fuel intensity of vessels in demersal and pelagic fisheries were strongly correlated with fish stock levels. The results highlighted the potential for stock rebuilding to reduce fuel intensity and furthermore suggested a potential policy instrument for reducing emission in ITQ-managed fisheries, in which harvesters own and trade individual emissions quota based on total allowable emissions for the fishery (Byrne, Agnarsson and Davidsdottir, 2021).
- 7) **Fishing gear - GHG emissions, Biodiversity loss, Acidification:** Although GHG emissions are often linked to resource efficiency and wider sustainability, this is not always the case, and it is important to avoid shifting burdens from climate to e.g. eutrophication or biodiversity impacts (Ziegler et al., 2024). In fisheries the impact of bottom trawling has been of concern because of potentially disturbing marine sediments resulting in negative impact on the marine ecosystem and biodiversity. Moreover, recent studies using carbon circulation models have revealed that amount of CO₂ exposed to sea surface enhanced by trawling is significant and impacting atmospheric CO₂ emissions and acidification (Atwood et al., 2024). The study emphasized the need for policy to avoid exclusive focus on avoided atmospheric emissions, as the results show that trawling-induced increases in DIC (dissolved inorganic carbon) in seawater could have severe implications for local or regional ocean acidification and importantly increase the estimated carbon footprint of the global fishing industry by over 200% within nine years (Atwood et al., 2024).

- 8) *Impact of feed*: In aquaculture the main GHG emissions are from the provision of feed components from agriculture production caused by the application of pesticides, fertilisers and use of fossil fuels on the farm (Pelletier et al., 2009, Winther et al., 2020).
- 9) *Waste recycling strategies* in the seafood supply chain are essential to tackle the growing seafood waste problem as outlined in the Waste Framework Directive (Commission Decision, 2011/753/EU, EU 2019) focusing on basic waste management principles with the preferred option of preventing waste. More effective waste management strategy would need to include waste minimization, characterizing the waste, and waste recycling (Cooney et al., 2024).
- 10) Various *sustainability metrics* have been used to assess the sustainability or efficiency of the utilization of the marine ingredient content of the feed in aquaculture. The ones commonly used in the marine ingredients sector include calculation of the use of forage fish in feed (eFIFO, FFDR, FIFO) and the efficiency of the feed (FCR). However, these metrics have been criticized because of the procedures in allocation and for not assessing the sustainability of the use of all feed ingredient resources on an equivalent basis e.g. the use of rest raw materials assigned as waste from e.g. demersal fisheries and processing. An alternative strategy is to assess the sustainability of marine ingredients based on a life cycle assessment (LCA) (Glencross et al., 2024).

Feed Fish Dependency Ratio (FFDR) is a measure used in the ASC standard for salmon/ Cermaq has reduced the use of marine raw materials in the feed reducing the Feed Fish Dependency Ratio and reports for fish meal (FFDRm) and for fish oil (FFDRo)
- 11) Refer to Oostdijk et al (2020) Catch–quota matching allowances balance economic and ecological targets in a fishery managed by individual transferable quota. In view of the trend toward individual quota and discard bans, the challenge for mixed fisheries includes how to avoid widespread underutilization of quota due to choking effects of individual species for which quota is exhausted. The issues include trade and catch–quota balancing allowances to fully utilize quota without discarding but this can theoretically lead to overfishing if total allowable catches (TACs) are consistently exceeded. *“When a vessel’s demersal catch exceeds owned and leased quota for a given species, the gap can be bridged by borrowing quota from the subsequent fishing period or transforming unutilized quota in other species, restricted by limits. Conversely, excess quota can be saved or transformed into quota for species where there is a shortfall. We found evidence that balancing behavior is frequently similar across the fleet. Transformations are consistent with indicators of a general quota shortage and potential for arbitrage caused by differences in conversion ratios used for transformation and lease prices”* the authors suggest policy changes that could further reduce ecological risks, e.g., prioritizing between-year transfers over transformations.

4. CONCLUSION

Our research findings on barriers to circular approaches and enhanced sustainability and the synthesis of challenges, leverage points and policy, show that realizing the potential of a more sustainable circular blue bioeconomy requires the development of target-based overarching strategies. Joint national and international initiatives, policies and standards have provided guidance for companies to enhance their sustainability performance. Large companies in the seafood sectors in Norway and Iceland are leaders in motivating sustainability in the blue bioeconomy as they partake in international initiatives which provide guidelines and standards as evidenced in their CSR or sustainability reports, however, performance of smaller companies is less visible.

Generally, the environmental sustainability reporting is on GHG emissions, energy use and waste management (e.g. solid waste to landfill). The new requirements of the ESRS on biodiversity and ecosystem challenges is partly addressed in CSR reports to date. The aquaculture companies have identified the main biological and nature related risks and formulated their own strategies and targets. KPIs are used to monitor e.g. topics related to animal welfare like escapes, sea-lice, use of medication which are also regulated and monitored. The ecosystem challenges like eutrophication and monitoring of sediments, freshwater use and wastewater discharge and the provision of sustainable feed ingredients are addressed in the sustainability reports. However, the reporting of resource use in terms of volumes of RRM is lacking and circularity reporting is mainly related to recycling of packaging material (plastics) and in the case of fisheries the recycling of fishing gear, while incentives to enhance recycling of biomaterial e.g. utilisation of RRM and closing resource loops will need more attention. Moreover, the double materiality concept requires reporting both direct impacts and challenges of the company including Scope 1-3 emissions, as well as possible financial risks from e.g. climate impacts which may originate from suppliers or downstream in the value chain or direct changes in physical conditions (e.g. ocean warming and acidification).

Improvements in approaches for CE assessment are needed to facilitate a transparent communication of the performance and notably, enhanced collaboration with the upstream and downstream actors and stakeholders involved in the supply chains is crucial to capture the whole life cycle of products and the circular activities.

The implementation of a more sustainable circular approach will need concerted efforts and collaboration among primary industry actors but also across primary, secondary and the whole ecosystem of service industries that have been built around the fisheries and aquaculture industries (primary industries). Taking a systemic view shows that improvements need to happen in tandem with improvements in other related and supporting industries.

The detailed synthesis of the results is published by the authors of this report (Saviolidis et al., 2025)¹⁸. The results also fed into WP5 T5.4 on the overall synthesis of SMARTCHAIN results and policy implications for sustainable circular business models and optimal utilization of resources in the blue bioeconomy¹⁹.

¹⁸ Saviolidis, N.M., Olafsdottir, G, Mehta S., Myhre, M.S., Strand, A.V. and Bogason, S (2025). Barriers in the transition to a more circular blue bioeconomy in Norway and Iceland: multistakeholder perspectives, Journal of Cleaner Production 521,146297, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2025.146297>

¹⁹ Olafsdottir, G., Saviolidis, N. M., Myhre, M. S., Mehta, S., Strand, A. V., Misimi, E., Skavang, P. K., Jiang, S., Larsen, A., Ghavamifar, A., Sigurðardóttir, H., Bogason, S., & Vasconcellos L. d'Oliveira Bouman, R. T. (2025). Circular sustainable business models Synthesis of overall results from the SMARTCHAIN project. Deliverable 5.4 Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15091142>

5. REFERENCES

- Atwood T.B., Romanou A., DeVries T., Lerner P.E., Mayorga J.S., Bradley D., Cabral, R.B., Schmidt, G.A. and Sala, E. (2024) Atmospheric CO₂ emissions and ocean acidification from bottom-trawling. *Front. Mar. Sci.* 10:1125137. doi: 10.3389/fmars.2023.1125137
- Ayer NW, Tyedmers PH, Pelletier, NL, Sonesson U, Scholz A (2007): Co-Product Allocation in Life Cycle Assessments of Seafood Production Systems: Review of Problems and Strategies. *Int J LCA* 12 (7) 480–487 DOI: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1065/lca2006.11.284>
- Axon, S. & Collier, S. (2022) Breaking Blue: Establishing comprehensive policy for a just and inclusive transition for the Blue Economy, *Marine Policy*, 147 (2023) 105343 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2022.105343>
- Bjørkan, M., & Eilertsen, S. M. (2020). Local perceptions of aquaculture: A case study on legitimacy from northern Norway. *Ocean & Coastal Management*, 195, 105276. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ocecoaman.2020.105276>
- Bocken, N., Short, S., Rana, P., Evans, S. (2013). A value mapping tool for sustainable business modelling. *Corporate Governance*, 13,5, 482-497. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CG-06-2013-0078>
- Boiral, O. Accounting for the Unaccountable: Biodiversity Reporting and Impression Management. *J Bus Ethics* 135, 751–768 (2016). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-014-2497-9>
- Boiral, O., & Heras-Saizarbitoria, I. (2020). Sustainability reporting assurance: Creating stakeholder accountability through hyperreality? *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 243, 118596. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2019.118596>.
- Boyd, C. E., McNevin, A. A., & Davis, R. P. (2022). The contribution of fisheries and aquaculture to the global protein supply. *Food Security*, 14, 805–827. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12571-021-01246-9>
- Carus, M. (2017). Biobased Economy and Climate Change—Important Links, Pitfalls, and Opportunities. *Industrial Biotechnology*, 13(2), 41–51. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1089/ind.2018.29121.mca>
- Chen, W., Jafarzadeh, S., Thakur, M., Ólafsdóttir, G., Mehta, S., Bogason, S., Holden, N.M. (2021) Environmental impacts of animal-based food supply chains with market characteristics, *Science of The Total Environment*, 783, 147077, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2021.147077>
- Cho, C. H., Michelon, G., & Patten, D. M. (2012). Impression Management in Sustainability Reports: An Empirical Investigation of the Use of Graphs. *Accounting and the Public Interest*, 12 (1), 16–37. <https://doi.org/10.2308/apin-10249>
- Clapp, J. (2021). The problem with growing corporate concentration and power in the global food system. *Nature Food*, 2(6), 404–408. doi:10.1038/s43016-021-00297-7
- COM (2019). *Blue Bioeconomy Forum: Roadmap for the blue bioeconomy*. Available at: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/613128>
- COM (2020). *Circular Economy Strategy*. Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/environment/circular-economy/>
- COM [European Commission] (2018). A sustainable bioeconomy for Europe: strengthening the connection between economy, society and the environment. Updated bioeconomy strategy. Publications Office. Retrieved from: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2777/792130>

- COM (2020). A new Circular Economy Action Plan: For a cleaner and more competitive Europe. Retrieved from: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/ALL/?uri=COM:2020:98:FIN>
- COM (2024). Revision of Directive 94/62/EC on Packaging and Packaging Waste (REFIT). In “A European Green Deal”. Accessed July 8, 2024 at: [https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-a-european-green-deal/file-revision-of-packaging-and-packaging-waste-directive-\(refit\)](https://www.europarl.europa.eu/legislative-train/theme-a-european-green-deal/file-revision-of-packaging-and-packaging-waste-directive-(refit))
- Cooney, R., de Sousa, D. B., Fernandez-Ríos, A., Mellett, S., Rowan, N., Morse, A. P., Hayes, M., Laso, J., Regueiro, L., Wan, A. H. L., & Clifford, E. (2023). A circular economy framework for seafood waste valorisation to meet challenges and opportunities for intensive production and sustainability. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 392, 136283. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2023.136283>
- Cristiano S., Baarset, H., Bruckner, C., Johansen, J., Pastres, R., (2022) Innovative options for the reuse and valorisation of aquaculture sludge and fish mortalities: Sustainability evaluation through Life-Cycle Assessment, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, Volume 352, 2022, 131613, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.131613>
- Dagiliene, L., Frenzel, M., Sutiene, K., Wnuk-Pel, T. (2020) Wise managers think about circular economy, wiser report and analyze it. Research of environmental reporting practices in EU manufacturing companies, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 274,121968, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.121968>
- Dauvergne & Lister (2012). Big brand sustainability: Governance prospects and environmental limits. *Global Environmental Change*, 22, 36–45. doi:10.1016/j.gloenvcha.2011.10.007
- Ellen MacArthur Foundation (2021) The Nature Imperative: How the circular economy tackles biodiversity loss
- Environmental Agency Iceland (nd) The national policy on waste reduction (Together against waste) by the Minister of the Environment and Natural Resources of Iceland is in effect from 2016-2027. Retrieved from <https://samangegnsoun.is/english/>
- Eyjólfsdóttir HR, Jónsdóttir H, Yngvadóttir E, Skúladóttir B (2003): Environmental Effects of Fish on the Consumers Dish – Life Cycle Assessment of Icelandic Frozen Cod products. Icelandic Fisheries Laboratories (IFL), Project report 06-03, Reykjavik, Island
- Foley, M. (2023, December 21). *France introduces possible jail time as penalty for non-compliance with sustainability disclosure.* Forbes. <https://www.forbes.com/sites/maryfoley/2023/12/21/france-introduces-possible-jail-time-as-penalty-for-non-compliance-with-sustainability-disclosure/>
- Fritsche et al., (2020). *Future transitions for the Bioeconomy towards sustainable development and a climate-neutral economy - Knowledge synthesis final report.* Publications Office of the European Union, Luxembourg.
- Galli, F., Prosperi, P., Favilli, E., D’Amico, S., Bartolini, F., Brunori, G. (2020) How can policy processes remove barriers to sustainable food systems in Europe? Contributing to a policy framework for agri-food transitions. *Food Policy*, 101871. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodpol.2020.101871>
- Geissdoerfer, M., Vladimirova, D., & Evans, S. (2018). Sustainable business model innovation: A review. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 198, 401e416. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2018.06.240>
- Geissdoerfer, M., Pieroni, M.P.P., Pigosso, D. C.A., Soufani, K. (2020) Circular business models: A review, *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 277, 123741 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2020.123741>

- Glencross, B.D., Bachis, E., Robb, D. & Newton, R. (2024). The Evolution of Sustainability Metrics for the Marine Ingredient Sector: Moving Towards Holistic Assessments of Aquaculture Feed, *Reviews in Fisheries Science & Aquaculture*, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1080/23308249.2024.2337426>
- Gottinger, A., Ladu, L., & Quitzow, R. (2020). Studying the transition towards a circular bioeconomy - A systematic literature review on transition studies and existing barriers. *Sustainability*, 12, 8990. doi:10.3390/su12218990
- Gudbrandsdottir, I.Y., Saviolidis, N.M., Olafsdottir, G., Oddsson, G.V., Stefansson, H., & Bogason, S.G. (2021). Transition pathways for the farmed salmon value chain: industry perspectives and sustainability implications. *Sustainability*, 13, 12106. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su132112106>
- Gunnlaugsson, S. B., & Valtysson, H. (2022). Sustainability and wealth creation, but no consensus: Recent decades in Iceland's ITQ-managed fisheries. *Marine Policy*, 135, 104836. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2021.104836>
- Hazaea, S.A., Zhu, J., Khatib, S.F.A. *et al.* Sustainability assurance practices: a systematic review and future research agenda. *Environ Sci Pollut Res* **29**, 4843–4864 (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-17359-9>
- Hala, A.F., Chougule, K., Cunha, M.E., Mendes, M.C., Oliveira, I., Bradley, T., Forbes, J., Speranza L.G. (2024). Life cycle assessment of integrated multi-trophic aquaculture: A review on methodology and challenges for its sustainability evaluation, *Aquaculture*, 590, 741035, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2024.741035>.
- Ho, O. T. K., Gajanayake, A., & Iyer-Rania, U. (2023). Transitioning to a state-wide circular economy: Major stakeholder interviews. *Resources, Conservation & Recycling Advances*, 19, 200163. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcradv.2023.200163>
- Holm, P., Raakjær, J., Jacobsen, R. B., & Henriksen, E. (2015). Contesting the social contracts underpinning fisheries—Lessons from Norway, Iceland and Greenland. *Marine Policy*, 55, 64-72. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2015.01.011>
- Ibáñez- Forés, V., Martínez-Sánchez, V., Valls-Val, K., Bovea M. D., (2022) Sustainability reports as a tool for measuring and monitoring the transition towards the circular economy of organisations: Proposal of indicators and metrics, *Journal of Environmental Management*, Volume 320, 115784, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2022.115784>
- Ministry for the Environment and Natural Resources (MENR) (2021). In view of the climate crisis: Iceland's Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change. Retrieved from: <https://www.government.is/topics/environment-climate-and-nature-protection/climate-change/adaptation/>
- Ministry for Foreign Affairs of Iceland (MFAI) (2021). Iceland's Policy on Matters Concerning the Arctic Region. Retrieved from: <https://www.government.is/publications/reports/report/2021/10/15/Iceland's-Policy-on-Matters-Concerning-the-Arctic-Region/>
- Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries (2016). The Government's bioeconomy strategy. Retrieved from: <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/historical-archive/solbergs-government/andre-dokumenter/nfd/2016/regjeringens-bioekonomistrategi-kjente-ressurser--uante-muligheter/id2521997/>
- Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries (MTIF) (2016). The Government's Bioeconomy Strategy: Familiar resources— undreamt of possibilities. Retrieved from: https://www.regjeringen.no/contentassets/32160cf211df4d3c8f3ab794f885d5be/bioekonomi-eng-kortversjon_uu.pdf

- Ministry of Trade, Industry and Fisheries (MTIF) (2021). The Government's commitment to the ocean and ocean industries: Blue Ocean, Green Future. Retrieved from: <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/dokumenter/the-governments-commitment-to-the-ocean-and-ocean-industries/id2857445/?ch=1>
- Nordic Council of Ministers (2015). Future Opportunities for Bioeconomy: Focus on the West Nordic Region. Retrieved from: <https://www.norden.org/en/publication/future-opportunities-bioeconomy>
- Nordic Council of Ministers (NCM) (2018). Nordic Bioeconomy Programme: 15 Action Points for Sustainable Change: Retrieved from: <https://norden.diva-portal.org/smash/record.jsf?pid=diva2%3A1222743&dsid=8878>
- Nordic Council of Ministers (NCM) (2021). Resilience in the blue bioeconomy: What can COVID-19 teach the Arctic about the impact of crises on value chains? Retrieved from: <https://pub.norden.org/nord2021-058/>
- Norwegian Institute of Bioeconomy Research (NIBIO) (2021). Sustainable Forestry in Norway. Accessed at: <https://www.skogbruk.nibio.no/>
- Kanbaty, M., Hellmann, A., & He, L (2020). Infographics in corporate sustainability reports: Providing useful information or used for impression management? *Journal of Behavioral and Experimental Finance*, 26, 100309. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbef.2020.100309>.
- Kanbaty, M., Hellmann, A., Ang, L. and He, L. (2024), "A review and analysis of impression management with photographs in sustainability reporting", *Meditari Accountancy Research*, Vol. 32 No. 3, pp. 976-1005. <https://doi.org/10.1108/MEDAR-09-2022-1798>
- Kirchherr, J., Reike, D., Hekkert, M. (2017). Conceptualizing the circular economy: An analysis of 114 definitions. *Resources, Conservation & Recycling*, 127, 221–232. doi: <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.09.005>
- Kirchherr, J., Yang, N.-H. N., Schulze-Spüntrup, F., Heerink, M. J., & Hartley, K. (2023). Conceptualizing the Circular Economy (Revisited): An Analysis of 221 Definitions. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 194, 107001. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2023.107001>
- Laso, J., Margallo, M., Celaya, J., Fullana, P., Bala, A., Gazulla, C., Irabien, A., Aldaco, R. (2016). Waste management under a life cycle approach as a tool for a circular economy in the canned anchovy industry. *Waste Manag. Res.*, 34 (8) (2016), pp. 724-733 <https://doi.org/10.1177/0734242X16652957>
- Linder, M. & Williander M. (2017) Circular business model innovation: inherent uncertainties, *Bus. Strat. Environ.*, 26 (2) (2017), pp. 182-196, <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.1906>
- Luthman, O., Jonell, M., Troell, M. (2019). Governing the salmon farming industry: Comparison between national regulations and the ASC salmon standard. *Marine Policy* 106, 103534 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2019.103534>
- Medows, D. (1999) Leverage Points - Places to Intervene in a system. The Sustainability Institute, Hartland, VT. Available at: https://www.donellameadows.org/wp-content/userfiles/Leverage_Points.pdf (Accessed 18.10.2024)
- MCE (2017): Ministry of Climate and Environment (2017). Better growth, lower emissions - the Norwegian Government's strategy for green competitiveness. Retrieved from:

- <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/dokumenter/bedre-vekst-lavere-utslipp--regjeringens-strategi-for-gronn-konkurranseskraft-engelsk/id2575420/>
- MENR (2021): The Ministry for the Environment and Natural Resources (2021). In view of the climate crisis: Iceland's Strategy on Adaptation to Climate Change. Retrieved from: <https://www.government.is/topics/environment-climate-and-nature-protection/climate-change/adaptation/>
- Misund, B., Molnár, P., Nguyen, Q. M., & Totland, E. (2024). Impact of rent taxation on Norwegian salmon farming companies. *Aquaculture Economics & Management*, 1–20. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/13657305.2024.2342268>
- Neff, R. A., Love, D. C., Overbey, K., Biehl, E., Deutsch, J., Gorski-Steiner, I., Pearson, P., Vigil, T., Turvey, C., & Fry, J.P. (2021). Consumer seafood waste and the potential of a 'Direct-from-Frozen' approach to prevention. *Foods*, 10, 2524. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/foods10112524>
- Nielsen, M., A. Hoff, R. Nielsen, P. Andersen, S. Waldo, C. Hammarlund, D. M. Kristofersson, S. Sævaldsson, J. Virtanen, J. Setälä, K. Roll, F. Asche, H. Rogvi, H. Ellefsen, Structural Adjustment and Regulation of Nordic Fisheries until 2025, TemaNord 2018:547, Nordic Council of Ministers, 2018. Retrieved from: <http://no-rden.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:1253233/FULLTEXT01.pdf>. a
- NMCE 2022a: Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment (2022). Norway's integrated plan for the conservation of areas of special importance for marine biodiversity. Retrieved from: <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/dokumenter/meld.-st.-29-20202021/id2843433/>
- NMCE 2022b: Norwegian Ministry of Climate and Environment (2022). Norwegian Plastics Strategy. Retrieved from: <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/dokumenter/norwegian-plastics-strategy/id2867004/>
- Office of the Prime Minister (2023). Norway - EU Green Alliance. Accessed at: <https://www.regjeringen.no/en/aktuelt/norway-and-eu-establish-green-alliance/id2973440/>
- Olafsdottir, G.; Mehta, S.; Richardsen, R.; Cook, D.; Gudbrandsdottir, I.Y.; Thakur, M.; Lane, A.; Bogason, S.G. Governance of the farmed salmon Value Chain from Norway to the EU. *Aquac. Eur.* 2019, 44, 5–19. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5494436>
- Olafsdottir, G., Saviolidis, N. M., Myhre, M. S., Mehta, S., Strand, A. V., Misimi, E., Skavang, P. K., Jiang, S., Larsen, A., Ghavamifar, A., Sigurðardóttir, H., Bogason, S., & Vasconcellos L. d'Oliveira Bouman, R. T. (2025). Circular sustainable business models Synthesis of overall results from the SMARTCHAIN project. Deliverable 5.4 Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15091142>
- Olsen, M. S., Amundsen, V. S., & Osmundsen, T. C. (2023). Exploring public perceptions and expectations of the salmon aquaculture industry in Norway: A social license to operate? *Aquaculture*, 574, 739632. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2023.739632>.
- Olsen, M. S., Amundsen, V. S., Alexander, K. A., Thorarinsdottir, R., Wilke, M., & Osmundsen, T. C. (2024). Social license to operate for aquaculture – A cross-country comparison. *Aquaculture*, 584, 740662. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2024.740662>
- Oostdijk, M., Byrne, C., Stefánsson G., and Woods, P.J. (2020) Catch–quota matching balance economic and ecological targets in a fishery managed by individual transferable

- quota. *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences (PNAS)* 117 (40) 24771-24777
<https://www.pnas.org/doi/full/10.1073/pnas.2008001117>
- Opferkuch, K., Caeiro S., Salomone, R., Ramos, T.B. (2021). Circular economy in corporate sustainability reporting: A review of organisational approaches. *Business Strategy and the Environment* 30(1) <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2854>
- Osmundsen, T.C.; Olsen, M.S. The imperishable controversy over aquaculture. *Mar. Policy* 2017, 76, 136–142. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2016.11.022>
- Philp, J. and Winickoff, D. (2018). “Realising the circular bioeconomy”, *OECD Science, Technology and Industry Policy Papers*, No. 60, OECD Publishing, Paris, <https://doi.org/10.1787/31bb2345-en>.
- Pieroni et al., (2019). Business model innovation for circular economy and sustainability: A review of approaches. *Journal of cleaner production*, 215, 198-216.
- Rector, M., Filgueira, R., Grant, J. (2024) The role of salmon aquaculture eco-certification in corporate social responsibility and the delivery of ecosystem services and disservices. *Marine Policy*, 160, February 2024, 105948 <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2023.105948>
- Redo, M. A., Che, M., Tolstorebrov, I., & Watanabe, M. (2024). CO₂-equivalent emissions and quality evaluation of chilled and frozen Atlantic salmon transported from Norway to Japan. *International Journal of Refrigeration*, in press. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijrefrig.2024.05.034>
- Regueiro, L., Newton, R., Soula, M., Méndez, D., Kok, B., Little, D. C., ... Ferreira, M. (2021). Opportunities and limitations for the introduction of circular economy principles in EU aquaculture based on the regulatory framework. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*. doi:10.1111/jiec.13188
- Richardson, J. (2008) The business model: an integrative framework for strategy execution. *Strat. Change*, 17 (5–6) (2008), pp. 133-144, <https://doi.org/10.1002/jsc.821>
- Ruiz-Salmón, I., Margallo, M., Laso, J., Villanueva-Rey, P., Mariño, D., Quinteiro, P., & Aldaco, R. (2020). Addressing challenges and opportunities of the European seafood sector under a circular economy framework. *Current Opinion in Environmental Science & Health*, 13, 101-106.
- Ruiz-Salmón, I., Laso, J., Margallo, M. et al., (2021) Life cycle assessment of fish and seafood processed products – A review of methodologies and new challenges, *Science of The Total Environment*, 761, 144094. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2020.144094>
- Slorach, P. C., Jeswani, H. K., Cuéllar-Franca, R., Azapagic, A., (2019) Environmental and economic implications of recovering resources from food waste in a circular economy. *Science of The Total Environment*, 693, 25, 133516. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.scitotenv.2019.07.322>
- Sousa-Zomer, T. T., Magalhães, L., Zancul, E., & Cauchick-Miguel, P. A. (2018). Exploring the challenges for circular business implementation in manufacturing companies: An empirical investigation of a pay-per-use service provider. *Resources, Conservation and Recycling*, 135, 3–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.resconrec.2017.10.033>
- Saviolidis, N. M., Davíðsdóttir, B., Ilmola, L., Stepanova, A., Valman, M., & Rovenskaya, E. (2020). Realising blue growth in the fishing industry in Iceland and Norway: Industry perceptions on drivers and barriers to blue growth investments and policy implications. *Marine Policy*, 117, 103967. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpol.2020.103967>

- Saviolidis, N.M.; Olafsdottir, G.; Nicolau, M.; Samoggia, A.; Huber, E.; Brimont, L.; Gorton, M.; von Berlepsch, D.; Sigurdardottir, H.; Del Prete, M.; et al. (2020) Stakeholder Perceptions of Policy Tools in Support of Sustainable Food Consumption in Europe: Policy Implications. *Sustainability* 2020, 12, 7161. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12177161>
- Saviolidis, N.M. and Olafsdottir, G. (2022). Sustainable resource use and circularity: Selected indicators. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TF). Deliverable: D3.1, University of Iceland, Reykjavík, 33 pages.
- Saviolidis, N.M., Olafsdottir, G, Mehta S., Strand, A.V. Myhre, M.S., and Bogason, S. (2023). Stakeholder engagement. Summary of results from stakeholder engagement activities in fisheries and aquaculture systems The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and Norges forskningsråd (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF). The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). Deliverable: D3.2, University of Iceland, Reykjavík, 28 pages
- Saviolidis, N.M., Olafsdottir, G, Mehta S., Myhre, M.S., Strand, A.V. and Bogason, S (2025). Barriers in the transition to a more circular blue bioeconomy in Norway and Iceland: multistakeholder perspectives, *Journal of Cleaner Production* 521,146297, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2025.146297>
- Strand A. V., Olafsdóttir, G., Saviolidis, N. M., Thakur, M. (2023) Data capture and information flows in seafood supply chains in Norway and Iceland. The SMARTCHAIN project co-funded by ERA-NET, EU Horizon 2020 G.A. No 817992, and the Norwegian Research Council (RCN), Innovation Fund Denmark (IDF), and The Icelandic Centre for Research (RANNIS) / Technical Development Fund (TDF). Deliverable: D1.3, SINTEF Ocean, Trondheim, 62 pages.
- Stegmann, P., Londo, M., & Junginger, M. (2020). The circular bioeconomy: Its elements and role in European bioeconomy clusters. *Resources, Conservation & Recycling*: X, 6. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rcrx.2019.100029>
- Svanes, E., Vold, M., Hanssen, O.J. (2011) Effect of different allocation methods on LCA results of products from wild-caught fish and on the use of such results. *Int. J. Life Cycle Assess.*, 16 (6) (2011), pp. 512-521, DOI 10.1007/s11367-011-0288-4
- Talbot, D., Boiral, O. (2018) GHG Reporting and Impression Management: An Assessment of Sustainability Reports from the Energy Sector. *J Bus Ethics* **147**, 367–383. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10551-015-2979-4>
- Thrane, M. LCA of Danish Fish Products. New methods and insights (9 pp). *Int J Life Cycle Assessment* **11**, 66–74 (2006). <https://doi.org/10.1065/lca2006.01.232>
- UNEP (2024). Global Bioeconomy Assessment: Coordinated Efforts of Policy, Innovation, and Sustainability for a Greener Future. Retrieved from: <https://wedocs.unep.org/handle/20.500.11822/45332>
- Valls-Val, K., Ibáñez-Forés, V., & Bovea, M.D. (2022). How can organisations measure their level of circularity? A review of available tools. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 354, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jclepro.2022.131679>
- Vigfússon, K., Jóhannsdóttir, L., Ólafsson, S. and Köseoğlu, M. (2024), "Key success factors for implementing strategy in the Icelandic fisheries industry", *Journal of Strategy and Management*, Vol. ahead-of-print No. ahead-of-print. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JSMA-04-2023-0069>

- Vince J., and Haward M. (2017), Hybrid governance of aquaculture: Opportunities and challenges. *Journal of Environmental Management* 201 138-144
- Winther, U., Skontorp Hognes, E., Jafarzadeh, S., Ziegler, F., 2020. Greenhouse Gas Emissions of Norwegian Seafood Products in 2017 SINTEF Ocean AS Report 2019:01505.
- Zharfpeykan, R. (2021). Representative account or greenwashing? Voluntary sustainability reports in Australia's mining/metals and financial services industries. *Business strategy and the environment*, 30(4), 2209-2223. doi: <https://doi.org/10.1002/bse.2744>
- Ziegler, F., Winther, U., Hognes, E. S., Emanuelsson, A., Sund, V., & Ellingsen, H. (2013). The carbon footprint of Norwegian seafood products on the global seafood market. *Journal of Industrial Ecology*, 17(1), 103-116.
- Ziegler F., Nistad, A.A., Langeland M., Wocken Y., Hognes, E.S., Mehta. S. (2024) Greenhouse gas emission reduction opportunities for the Norwegian salmon farming sector - can they outweigh growth? *Aquaculture*, 581, 74043, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.aquaculture.2023.740431>
- Zeppenfeldt, L., Dinesh, D., Vellema, S., (2024) Five paradoxes navigated by incumbent private sector firms moving towards climate-oriented innovation in food systems. *Front. Sustain. Food Syst.*, 09 October 2024, Sec. Social Movements, Institutions and Governance, Volume 8 - 2024 | <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2024.1436302>
- Zeppenfeldt et al (2024) The role of large private sector firms in rerouting our food systems towards sustainability through climate-oriented innovation is highly contested. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fsufs.2024.1436302>
- Ögmundarson, Ó., Kalweit, L.S., Venkatachalam, V., Kristjánsdóttir, R., Endres, H.-J., & Spierling, S. (2022). Plastic packaging waste management in Iceland: challenges and opportunities from a Life Cycle Assessment perspective. *Sustainability*, 14, 16837. doi: <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142416837>

ANNEX I

Table 8 List of the largest fisheries companies in Iceland according to catch volumes (Aflamark) in 2022-2023 and information on sustainability reporting and certifications from their websites (From Deliverable 3.2).

Company	Website /info	Sustainability report /year first published	Guidelines	SFS Policy signed	Certifications* and memberships (Initiatives)
Síldarvinnslan hf. SVN	IS	Yes / 2019	GRI /SFS /ESG	Yes	MSC, Global TRUST (IFFO), IRF, FEMAS (feed material assurance), Tún /Naturland (organic), GFSI (BRC)
Brim hf	IS/EN	Yes / 2017	GRI /SFS /ESG	Yes	MSC, IRF, GSSI
Ísfélag hf. (Rammi)	IS/EN	YES /2021	GRI	Yes	Global TRUST, MSC, HACCP, FEMAS, TÚN organic
Samherji Ísland ehf	IS/EN	No	N/A	Yes	MSC, IRF, BRC, GFSI, BAP
Vinnlustöðin hf. Huginn	IS/EN	No	N/A	No Yes	MSC, IRF, HACCP
Eskja hf.	IS/EN	YES / EN 2021	GRI /SFS /ESG	Yes	MSC; Equal pay ÍST85:2012: IFFO&FEMAS, Tún organic production
Skinney-Þinganes hf.	IS/EN	YES / IS 2021	GRI /SFS /ESG	Yes	Gender equality ÍST85:2012: IFS/GFSI; MSC; IFFO&FEMAS
Gjögur hf.	No	No	N/A	Yes	MSC
Loðnavinnslan hf.	IS	No	N/A	Yes	MSC, Gender Equal pay IST 85:2012
FISK Seafood ehf.	IS/EN	Yes / IS 2021	GRI /SFS /ESG	Yes	IFS, MSC, IRF, Equal pay ÍST85:2012
Thorfish (Þorbjörn hf.)	IS	Yes / IS 2021	GRI /SFS /ESG	Yes	MSC IRF, ISF
Nesfiskur ehf.	IS	No	N/A	Yes	MSC Gender equal pay ÍST85:2012
Hraðfrystihúsið - Gunnvör hf.	IS/EN	No	N/A	Yes	IRF
Útgerðarfélag Reykjavíkur hf	EN	No (public financial statements)	N/A	Yes	MSC, IRF
Vísir hf (Síldarvinnslan)	IS	YES /IS / 2020	GRI /SFS /ESG	Yes	MSC, IRF, BRC Equal pay ÍST 85:2012, Long line caught

Sustainability reports are prepared in accordance with the GRI Standard (Global Reporting Initiative GRI) and **SFS sustainability policy** based on the UN SDGs, ESG reporting guide 2.0 (Fisheries Iceland and Nasdaq's ESG guidelines, translated to Icelandic)